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D4.2 Validation methods for AI-based decision support systems

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Abstract

This task involved the development of a guideline for the external validation of Artificial Intelligence-based Clinical Decision Support Systems (AI-CDSS) using local real-world data (RWD) at the pre-deployment, post-regulatory approval stage (VALID-AI - VALIDation of Local Indicators in the pre-Deployment phase of AI-CDSS). This was constructed through a two-round Delphi process involving a panel of international and multidisciplinary experts, in order to refine and standardize external validation approaches through expert-driven consensus.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2 Validation methods for AI-based decision support systems) is part of Task 4.2 (WP4 DHT Assessment Framework, Toolkit and Manual), led by Fundación Progreso y Salud (FPS) with the involvement of TUD, UOXF, and NICE. The task addresses a critical gap between regulatory approval and local clinical adoption of AI-based Clinical Decision Support Systems (AI-CDSS). While many AI tools obtain CE marking or FDA approval, their performance and safety in local populations often remain untested, creating risks for patient safety and barriers to adoption.

To close this gap, D4.2 describes VALID-AI (VALidation of Local Indicators in the pre-Deployment phase of AI-CDSS), a guideline for the external validation of AI-CDSS using local Real-World Data (RWD) in the pre-deployment, post-regulatory phase. VALID-AI provides methodological and practical guidance to ensure algorithms demonstrate accuracy, robustness, reproducibility, generalizability, fairness, and clinical relevance before being integrated into local workflows.

The work builds on challenges identified in WP2 and draws on existing frameworks such as DECIDE-AI and TRIPOD-AI, adapted to a later stage of the AI lifecycle (external validation in local datasets). VALID-AI was developed through a Delphi consensus process, involving two electronic rounds with international and multidisciplinary experts (clinicians, AI specialists, regulators, methodologists, HTA professionals). Items with $\geq 80\%$ agreement (score ≥ 4 on a 1–5 Likert scale) were retained, while those with 70–80% agreement — as well as a few items below 70% — were discussed during a Consensus Meeting held on October 6th, 2025. This process helped refine VALID-AI in terms of its final section structure, item composition, and guideline wording.

VALID-AI is structured around three thematic blocks, reflecting the chronological sequence of external validation with RWD:

1. Pre-validation requirements – dataset documentation, cohort comparisons, and recommended good practices such as adherence to FAIR principles.
2. Operational steps for external validation – performance metrics, bias and fairness analysis, explainability and interpretability, governance of performance criteria and revalidation triggers, and recommended good practices.
3. Post-deployment best practices for validation and monitoring – governance of validation cycles, fairness reporting, stakeholder engagement, regulatory alignment, and strategies for sustainable deployment.

The guideline consists of two main components:

- ▶ A Reporting Item Checklist, summarising essential items for external validation.
- ▶ An Explanation and Elaboration (E&E) section, providing detailed recommendations and good practice guidance.

In addition, a Glossary of Terms was developed to harmonise terminology and illustrate practical applications.

By providing a standardised and consensus-based framework, VALID-AI supports model developers and validators, HTA bodies, and healthcare institutions in evaluating AI-CDSS with local RWD, reducing risks, and improving transparency, reproducibility, and equity. Ultimately, the guideline will help ensure that AI systems move from regulatory approval to safe, effective and fair adoption in real-world clinical practice.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is part of Task 4.2 of Work Package 4, focused on the development of validation methods for clinical decision support systems (CDSS) based on artificial intelligence (AI).

1.1 Context

In recent decades, AI has taken a central role in healthcare systems, becoming an increasingly important tool not only for supporting disease diagnosis but also for managing healthcare resources. Evidence suggests that the effective application of AI in healthcare can significantly improve patient outcomes and the quality of care, while simultaneously enhancing efficiency and effectiveness (1). These AI models can be developed using retrospective data, such as electronic health records (EHR), and once thoroughly validated, they can be integrated into CDSS that have undergone regulatory approval. These systems are deployed in hospitals to assist clinicians in making informed decisions (2).

Ensuring the safety and effectiveness of AI-based healthcare products, alongside navigating regulatory approval, remains a highly complex challenge. In the United States, agencies such as the FDA, FTC, and the Department of Health and Human Services (including the ONC), are involved in this process (3). In Europe, the European Commission's DG-SANTE, national health ministries, competent authorities, notified bodies, HTA agencies, MDCG, and EMA play pivotal roles (4). In the face of these challenges, several governmental and non-governmental partner organisations have proposed specific frameworks for the evaluation of AI systems, providing crucial guidance to health systems, governments and stakeholders considering the adoption of AI tools (5).

In addition, the European Commission has developed the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) (6), which outlines seven key requirements for trustworthy AI, including transparency, robustness, data governance, and accountability. More recently, the adoption in 2024 of the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) (7) has introduced a binding regulatory framework that classifies AI systems according to risk. AI-CDSS are typically considered high-risk applications, requiring strict conformity assessment procedures, post-market monitoring, and human oversight obligations. While both ALTAI and the AI Act establish essential principles and regulatory requirements, they do not directly address how AI-CDSS should be clinically validated in local healthcare contexts after regulatory approval. Furthermore, by the time VALID-AI applies (covering the post-regulatory, pre-deployment phase), AI-CDSS will therefore already have complied with the European regulatory requirements for AI, and the guideline focuses on the subsequent need for local validation prior to clinical adoption. VALID-AI aims to complement these frameworks by providing practical, consensus-based guidance on external validation with real-world data (RWD), ensuring alignment with regulatory expectations while filling the methodological gap needed for safe and effective adoption in clinical practice.

Despite these established frameworks, as highlighted by Sammy Chouffani El Fassi et al. (8), there exists a significant gap between regulatory oversight and the proper validation of AI models, including machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models, when applied to local population data. This gap raises potential risks to patient safety. In this context, Alexey Youssef et al. (9) underscored the importance of conducting both internal and external validation to ensure the reliability of these models. Similarly, a systematic review by Katarzyna Kolasa et al. noted gaps in both internal and external validation of ML systems and noted a need for more accessibility to healthcare data to ease the adoption of these systems into clinical practice (10).

In response to these limitations, the present guideline aims to address the lack of such strategies by developing and refining methods to guide the external validation of AI-CDSS using RWD. These methods are designed to enable developers and healthcare decision-makers to assess whether the performance of an algorithm is equally robust in local populations compared to those in which the algorithm was initially developed.

1.2 Scope

To situate VALID-AI within the broader ecosystem of reporting and evaluation frameworks, it is important to acknowledge the EQUATOR-network guidelines that have shaped methodological standards for AI in healthcare research. Some of these guidelines focus primarily on clinical trials: CONSORT-AI extends the Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials to randomized controlled trials involving AI interventions, while SPIRIT-AI provides complementary guidance for the design and reporting of clinical trial protocols that incorporate AI systems. Other initiatives are more directly linked to the development and validation of predictive algorithms: TRIPOD-ML, an extension of TRIPOD, offers methodological and reporting recommendations specific to machine learning–based prediction models, and STARD-AI (currently in development) adapts the diagnostic accuracy reporting standards to AI-driven diagnostic tools.

Of particular relevance to this D4.2 is DECIDE-AI, which addresses the early-stage clinical evaluation of AI-based decision support systems, focusing on “silent” or “shadow” mode testing in live settings prior to full deployment. DECIDE-AI plays a crucial role in the AI-CDSS lifecycle by bridging the gap between *in silico* evaluation and prospective clinical trials. However, it does not extend into the post-regulatory, pre-deployment phase, which is where VALID-AI is positioned. By building on the foundations established by DECIDE-AI and other EQUATOR guidelines, VALID-AI fills this distinct gap by providing structured methods and consensus-based recommendations for the external and local validation of AI-CDSS using RWD. This ensures that algorithms proven effective in development and early trials can be robustly assessed for safety, fairness, and clinical relevance in the local populations and healthcare environments where they are intended to be deployed.

In this deliverable, we define what an external validation protocol should include during the pre-deployment phase, that is, the stage after the AI system has obtained commercialization permissions (e.g., FDA approval or CE mark) but before it is implemented in real-world clinical practice. At this stage, the model has not yet been tested on a specific local population outside the training dataset, to confirm its effectiveness and relevance within that particular context (e.g., a specific hospital or region). This positioning is illustrated by the green circle in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Within AI-CDSS development, our Delphi is focused on the development of validation methods for CDSS based on AI pre-deployment local validation utilising RWD.

1.3 Methods

As of October 2025, the VALID-AI guideline has completed a two-round Delphi process followed by a Consensus Meeting, representing a near-final version of the guideline to be published. VALID-AI was developed through a structured Delphi consensus methodology involving two electronic rounds with international and multidisciplinary experts, including clinicians, AI specialists, regulators, methodologists, and HTA professionals. Items achieving $\geq 80\%$ agreement (score ≥ 4 on a 1–5 Likert scale) were retained, while those with 70–80% agreement — as well as a few items below 70% — were discussed during the Consensus Meeting held on October 6th, 2025. This iterative process refined the final section structure, item composition, and wording of the VALID-AI guideline.

This guideline supports the goal of assessing the accuracy and safety of AI-CDSS via the following:

- Enhancing validation through expert consensus: Applying a two-round Delphi methodology with a multidisciplinary panel and a Consensus Meeting strengthens the recommended external validation practices. By integrating diverse perspectives and experiences, the process helped identify and address gaps in current methods. Expert contributions helped refine and adapt validation protocols to the specific challenges and needs of AI systems in healthcare contexts.
- Leveraging RWD for robust evaluation: Incorporating RWD in the validation process provides a more accurate evaluation of how CDSS perform under real-world clinical conditions. This is crucial to ensure that algorithms are effective in clinical practice scenarios and not just in controlled or theoretical environments.
- Supporting the post-regulatory approval phase: Improved validation guidance is expected to facilitate the post-regulatory approval phase. By relying on expert-agreed validation methods, the effectiveness and safety of AI systems can be demonstrated more convincingly, thereby supporting their implementation and adoption in local clinical environments.

In this context, it is crucial to acknowledge the following key concepts relevant to pre-deployment local validation using RWD (PLV-RWD):

- *External Validation* involves strategies designed to assess the predictive capability of models when applied to new data points.
- *Real World Data (RWD)* refers to information gathered from patients within a local population, specifically from hospital/s or healthcare system/s where the algorithm will be implemented. Such data are vital for validating and evaluating AI-based CDSS to ensure their effectiveness and relevance within the local healthcare environment.

In summary, the purpose of this guideline is for the external validation of AI-based CDSS using local RWD at the pre-deployment, post-regulatory approval stage. This was constructed through consultation with a panel of international and multidisciplinary experts, in order to refine and standardize validation approaches through expert-driven consensus.

1.4 Guideline Overview

This guideline is structured around three thematic blocks aligned with the main phases of PLV-RWD, following a chronological sequence:

- ▶ **Block 1** covers pre-validation requirements, such as data documentation from model developers and validators, cohort comparisons, and good practices like adherence to FAIR principles.
- ▶ **Block 2** focuses on how to operationalize external validation, including performance metric selection based on the clinical use case, bias and fairness analysis, explainability and interpretability, governance of performance criteria and revalidation triggers, and good practices.
- ▶ **ANNEX: Block 3** addresses post-validation considerations, covering validation and monitoring aspects such as the governance of validation cycles, fairness reporting, stakeholder communication, regulatory alignment, and long-term deployment strategies.

In this context, two roles are distinguished in this process

- ▶ **Model developers**, who design and build the AI-CDSS and have obtained regulatory approval or market authorization in at least one country or region.
- ▶ **Model validators**, who perform the external validation of the AI-CDSS using local data (e.g., a Local Data Validation Team) and assess the resulting evidence to establish recommendations for clinical decision-making (e.g., an HTA body). These two roles may belong to the same institution or to different organizations, but must work with local data from the setting in which the AI-CDSS is intended to be deployed.

The present guideline consists of two main components:

- ▶ **Reporting Item Checklist:** a table summarizing the items selected by experts for inclusion in the final guideline.
- ▶ **Explanation and Elaboration:** detailed descriptions and recommendations accompanying each item.

To promote clarity and a shared understanding, a comprehensive **Glossary of Terms** (ANNEX I) is provided, defining and expanding upon the key concepts used throughout the guideline.

2 Reporting Item Checklist

Table 1. Reporting Item Checklist of the VALID-AI guideline

Item Index	Description	Reported on page
<u>Block 1: Previous External Validation Requirements</u>		
1.1	Preliminary information from the training dataset (model developers)	
1.1.1.	Research question	
1.1.2.	Clinical impact	
1.1.3.	Source and target population characteristics	
1.1.4.	Inclusion/exclusion criteria	
1.1.5.	Independent variables and outcome	
1.1.6.	Development data dictionary	
1.1.7.	Data preprocessing steps	
1.1.8.	Dataset splits (train/test/validation)	
1.1.9.	Table of baseline characteristics	
1.1.10.	AI model specifications	
1.1.11.	Performance metrics	
1.1.12.	Bias and fairness analysis	
1.1.13.	Model calibration	
1.1.14.	Model explainability	
1.1.15.	Definition of use cases and testing scenarios	
1.1.16.	Model readiness for external validation	
1.2	Preliminary information from the external validation dataset (model validators)	
1.2.1.	Table of baseline characteristics	
1.2.2.	Validation data dictionary	
1.2.3.	Data quality	
1.2.4.	Minimum sample size	
1.2.5.	Definition of use cases and testing scenarios	
1.3	Comparison between training and external validation cohorts	
1.3.1.	Comparison between training and validation cohorts	
1.3.2.	Bias management framework and comparative bias assessment	
1.3.3.	Analysis and comparison of social determinants of health (SDH)	

1.3.4.	Interoperability - technical compatibility	
1.3.5.	Interoperability - semantic compatibility	
1.4	Good practices	
1.4.1.	Public code and full methodology documentation	
1.4.2.	FAIR principles compliance	
<u>Block 2: Operational Steps for External Validation</u>		
2.1	Performance metrics across different scenarios	
2.1.1.	Regression scenarios	
2.1.2.	Binary classification scenarios	
2.1.3.	Multi-class classification scenarios	
2.2	Bias and fairness analysis	
2.2.1.	Data collection bias	
2.2.2.	Algorithmic bias	
2.2.3.	Fairness analysis	
2.3	Explainability and interpretability	
2.3.1.	Explainability techniques	
2.3.2.	Criteria for validating explainability and interpretability	
2.3.3.	Explainability review and interpretation	
2.3.4.	Examples of XAI use cases	
2.4	Governance of performance criteria and revalidation triggers	
2.4.1.	Recommended minimum performance thresholds	
2.4.2.	Triggers for initiating additional validation cycles	
2.5	Good practices	
2.5.1.	Public code and full methodology documentation	
2.5.2.	Version control, collaborative documentation, and audit trails	
2.5.3.	Definition and assessment of clinical utility	
2.5.4.	Stakeholder communication and reporting	
<u>ANNEX - Block 3: Post-Deployment Best Practices for Validation and Monitoring (OPTIONAL)</u>		
3.1	Governance of validation cycles	
3.1.1.	Frequency of periodic local validation cycles	
3.1.2.	Number of local validation iterations for stability	
3.2	Discrimination analysis, fairness reporting, and ethical alignment	
3.2.1.	Ongoing fairness reporting	

3.2.2.	Discrimination disclosure	
3.2.3.	Promoting ethical use	
3.3	Stakeholder and end-user involvement	
3.3.1.	Multidisciplinary team leadership	
3.3.2.	Inclusion of diverse backgrounds	
3.3.3.	End-user feedback	
3.4	Regulatory and open science considerations	
3.4.1.	Compliance with evolving regulatory frameworks	
3.4.2.	Open science principles	
3.5	Post-deployment monitoring and long-term adoption	
3.5.1.	Monitoring of real-world use and performance	
3.5.2.	Education and behavioural strategies	
3.5.3.	Evaluation of real-world clinical impact	
3.5.4.	Operational long-term sustainability	

3 Explanation & Elaboration

Block 1: Previous External Validation Requirements

Block 1 outlines the information, documentation, and preparatory steps that should be completed before initiating external validation on local data. It specifies the responsibilities of model developers and validators in providing transparent documentation of the datasets, data provenance, preprocessing steps, and model specifications. The block also defines standards for assessing data quality, comparability between training and validation cohorts, bias management framework, and FAIR compliance. Together, these items ensure that the model is sufficiently documented, technically ready, and ethically sound to proceed with external validation using local data.

1.1. Preliminary information from the training dataset (model developers)

This section outlines the preliminary information that model developers should provide to model validators (Local Data Validation Team) regarding the model and its training data. The items are organized according to the IMRaD structure (Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion) to promote clarity and consistency in documentation.

Introduction

- 1.1.1. *Research question:* Clearly define the main research objective that the AI-CDSS is designed to address.
- 1.1.2. *Clinical impact and risk classification:* Describe the specific clinical decision the AI-CDSS aims to support and its potential impact within healthcare settings.
Model developers should also specify the model's regulatory risk classification (e.g., according to the EU AI Act or MDR/IVDR framework), explaining how it aligns with the intended use and clinical consequences of incorrect predictions. This information helps model validators tailor validation requirements proportionally to the model's risk level.

Methods and Results

- 1.1.3. *Source and target population characteristics:* Describe both the development dataset population and the intended target population where the model is expected to be applied. Include relevant demographics and clinical characteristics at a general level, as well as information on data provenance—such as the type of healthcare centre(s) (hospital, private clinic, community clinic, etc), geographical region or country, healthcare system, and overall patient volume.
- 1.1.4. *Inclusion/exclusion criteria:* Describe the criteria used to select patients for the dataset(s) used in model development, including years of data collection, diagnosis, age range, treatment type, etc.

- 1.1.5. *Independent variables and outcome*: Provide clear definitions of all input features (independent variables) used by the model and the specific clinical outcome it predicts.
- 1.1.6. *Development data dictionary*: Include variable names, descriptions, types (categorical/continuous), time window specifications, units, and value ranges for all dataset variables.
- 1.1.7. *Data preprocessing steps and quality checking*: Describe all preprocessing steps (e.g., missing data imputation, outlier removal, transformation of variables) and data quality checks (See Item 1.2.3 for detailed guidance on data quality).
- 1.1.8. *Dataset splits (train/test/validation)*: Documentation of how the dataset was partitioned for model training, internal testing, and development validation, including proportions, methodology (e.g., random, stratified), and any relevant stratifying factors.
- 1.1.9. *Table of baseline characteristics*: Present a summary table of descriptive statistics for the development population, including key demographic and clinical variables. Report sample size and distribution within each relevant subgroup or class (e.g., sex, age, comorbidities, outcome categories). Include appropriate summary measures (e.g., mean, median, SD, IQR, or proportions) and indicate missingness rates when relevant.
- 1.1.10. *AI model specifications*: Describe the final algorithm family type and best-performing model, including its architecture or key parameters, cross-validation strategy, and the chosen prediction threshold and its rationale.
- 1.1.11. *Performance metrics*: List relevant performance metrics evaluated during train/testing, and indicate which were selected to optimize the final model, including those used in hyperparameter tuning.
- 1.1.12. *Bias and fairness analysis*: Summarize the methods and findings from bias and fairness analyses conducted during model development, detailing any identified disparities across relevant subgroups (e.g., sex, age, ethnicity) using specific fairness metrics (See item 1.3.3. on social determinants of health and section 2.2 on bias and fairness, for detailed guidance).
- 1.1.13. *Model calibration*: When applicable, report calibration metrics (e.g., Brier score, calibration plots, reliability diagrams) to evaluate the agreement between predicted and observed outcomes. Stratify results by relevant subgroups to assess the reliability and consistency of model predictions across populations.
- 1.1.14. *Model explainability*: Present key insights gained from model explainability analyses, including descriptions of the explainability methods used (e.g., SHAP, LIME, feature importance scores, Grad-CAM).

Discussion

- 1.1.15. *Definition of use cases and testing scenarios*: Describe the model developers' intended use cases and predefined high-risk clinical situations. This information supports realistic

evaluation and stress-testing of the model under expected and critical conditions in clinical practice.

- 1.1.16. *Model readiness for external validation*: Evaluate whether the model is sufficiently documented and technically prepared for PLV-RWD, including any assumptions made during training, limitations, and modifications needed to ensure safe and reliable performance in a new clinical environment.

1.2. Preliminary information from the external validation dataset (model validators)

This section specifies the recommended information to be collected and the procedures to be conducted by model validators (Local Data Validation Team) regarding the local dataset used for external validation. Understanding these characteristics ensures that the dataset is suitable for assessing the model's generalizability, robustness, and performance in a new clinical context.

- 1.2.1. *Table of baseline characteristics*: Present a summary table of descriptive statistics for the development population, including key demographic and clinical variables. Report sample size and distribution within each relevant subgroup or class (e.g., sex, age, comorbidities, outcome categories). Include appropriate summary measures (e.g., mean, median, SD, IQR, or proportions) and indicate missingness rates when relevant.
- 1.2.2. *Validation data dictionary*. Include variable names, descriptions, types (categorical/continuous), time window specifications, units, and value ranges for all dataset variables.
- 1.2.3. *Data quality*: Confirm whether the local validation dataset meets robust data quality standards, as insufficient quality may introduce bias and compromise the effectiveness, safety, and equity of AI-based CDSS. The following dimensions should be considered and documented:
 - Uniqueness: Verify that each record represents a distinct entity (e.g., a single patient encounter) and that no duplicates exist. Duplicated entries can distort statistical analyses and overrepresent certain individuals or outcomes.
 - Consistency: Assess whether data values comply with logical, statistical, and syntactic rules within and across variables. Consistent datasets maintain internal coherence and reduce errors caused by mismatched or contradictory information.
 - Correctness: Confirm that data accurately represents real-world events or measurements, captured with the appropriate level of precision for its intended clinical or analytical use.
 - Timeliness: Evaluate whether the data is current, up-to-date, and available within an appropriate timeframe for its intended purpose. This includes assessing data collection and processing delays that may reduce clinical relevance.
 - Completeness: Determine whether all mandatory fields, conditionally required variables, and relevant population segments are represented. Missing or incomplete data can impair reliability, particularly in model retraining and validation.

- **Stability:** Examine whether data remains consistent over time and across sources, ensuring that any observed variations reflect true changes in the underlying population rather than artefacts of data collection.
- **Representativeness:** Evaluate the extent to which the dataset reflects the characteristics of the target population. A representative dataset supports generalizable and equitable model validation.
- **Trustworthiness:** Assess the reliability, authenticity, and governance of data sources, ensuring compliance with ethical, legal, and technical standards. Trustworthy data enhances confidence in model validation results.
- **Contextualization:** Ensure that adequate metadata and provenance information (e.g., data source, transformation steps, responsible entities) are available to interpret and reuse the dataset appropriately, supporting transparency and reproducibility.

1.2.4. *Minimum sample size:* Determine the minimum required population size needed to ensure a statistically robust and generalizable external validation. Confirm whether the external dataset meets this requirement, particularly for the outcome of interest and key subgroups, to support reliable performance assessment. It is recommended to use statistical power calculators to estimate the appropriate sample size.

1.2.5. *Definition of use cases and testing scenarios:* From the model validators' perspective (Local Data Validation Team and HTA body), review and confirm whether the intended clinical use cases and high-risk or critical scenarios —as previously defined by the model developers— are represented and applicable in the external validation dataset. This helps ensure that stress-testing and performance evaluation are aligned with real-world conditions in the local context.

1.3. Comparison between training and external validation cohorts

This section focuses on a comparative review between the training and external validation datasets. While model developers have already provided detailed information about the training data in Section 1.1, model validators (Local Data Validation Team) are responsible for assessing similarities and differences with the local dataset to confirm its suitability for validation. The goal is to ensure that any observed differences are properly understood and addressed before conducting external validation by identifying meaningful variations in population structure and potential sources of bias or interoperability issues that could affect model performance.

1.3.1. *Comparison between training and validation cohorts:* Assess the alignment and comparability of the development, and external validation datasets to ensure the model's generalizability and relevance. This includes evaluating consistency in variable definitions, availability, operationalization, and data collection frequency, as well as identifying discrepancies in data dictionaries (e.g., variable names, formats, types, time windows, units, or value ranges) that could affect compatibility or interpretation. Additionally, compare key demographic and clinical characteristics using descriptive statistics and appropriate statistical tests to detect meaningful differences in population structure and potential sources of bias or interoperability issues. If relevant differences are identified, consider applying appropriate statistical techniques—such as propensity score matching

or stratified analyses—to adjust for potential confounding and improve cohort comparability.

- 1.3.2. *Bias management framework and comparative bias assessment*: Implement a structured process to identify, measure, mitigate, and monitor bias throughout model development and external validation. This includes detecting relevant sources of bias (e.g., human bias such as cognitive, historical, population, social, or behavioural; and data-related bias such as measurement, representation, sampling, temporal, or omitted-variable bias) and evaluating whether these biases persist, shift, or newly emerge in the external validation dataset.

Define fairness objectives, select appropriate bias and fairness metrics, and involve interdisciplinary teams to interpret findings and guide mitigation strategies. Use disaggregated performance metrics to detect disparities across vulnerable populations, apply balancing or fairness-aware techniques when necessary, and reassess fairness at each validation and deployment stage to ensure equitable model performance across distinct populations.

- 1.3.3. *Analysis and comparison of social determinants of health (SDH)*: Assess whether relevant differences in social determinants of health (SDH) between the training and external validation cohorts could introduce bias or affect model fairness and generalizability. The following categories are recommended for structured assessment:

- Age: Classify participants by life-stage categories, as age often interacts with disease incidence, treatment response, and data availability. Suggested categories: Childhood (0–9 years), Adolescence (10–19 years), Youth (20–24 years), Adulthood (25–64 years), Older age (≥65 years).
- Sex: Identify the biological sex of participants (Female, Male, or Intersex, when available).
- Ethnicity and race: Capture major ethnic or racial categories as available in local datasets, such as African American, Asian, Caucasian, Hispanic, Native American, Other/Unknown.
- Socioeconomic level: When possible, provide socioeconomic level categories to identify potential inequities in model performance. Suggested dimensions:
 - Education level (no formal education, primary, secondary, higher education)
 - Health literacy / language comprehension
 - Employment status (employed, unemployed, retired, student, other)
 - Income level (e.g., quartiles or national poverty thresholds)
 - Food security (stable, moderate insecurity, severe insecurity)
 - Housing security (own, rent, unstable, homeless)
 - Living environment (urban, suburban, rural; overcrowding; pollution exposure).
- Situation of disability. If available, report disability using international standards such as the Washington Group Short Set (WG-SS), which defines six domains of disability assessed on a severity scale (no difficulty, some difficulty, a lot of difficulty, cannot do at all). Domains:

- Seeing
 - Hearing
 - Walking or climbing steps
 - Remembering or concentrating
 - Self-care
 - Communicating
- Healthcare access and quality. Assess structural and individual differences in access to and quality of healthcare between datasets. Suggested dimensions:
 - Healthcare coverage type: public, private, mixed.
 - Access to primary care: regular GP visits, emergency-only care, none.
 - Specialist availability and waiting times.
 - Continuity and coordination of care: single vs. multiple care providers.
 - Geographic accessibility: travel distance/time to nearest healthcare facility.
 - Data source type: tertiary hospital, primary care, regional network.
 - Working conditions. When available, report information on patients' working conditions, as a component of SDH. Suggested categories include:
 - Employment status: employed, unemployed, retired, student, or other.
 - Type of occupation: manual labour, non-manual/office work, healthcare, education, services, agriculture, etc.
 - Work environment and physical demands: sedentary, standing, physically demanding, exposure to noise, chemicals, or extreme temperatures.
 - Work schedule and stability: full-time, part-time, temporary, shift work, night work.
 - Work-related risks or hazards: exposure to biological agents, heavy lifting, repetitive strain, psychosocial stress, or unsafe conditions.
 - Social support.

When available, report indicators of social or community support, as these may influence model generalizability and patient outcomes. Suggested categories include:

 - Living situation: living alone, with family, in assisted living, or in a nursing home.
 - Type of social support: informal (family, friends, caregivers) or formal/institutional (community programs, home care services).
 - Integration of support: degree of coordination between healthcare and social care (e.g., integrated support in nursing homes or community-based care).
 - Access to social services: availability and frequency of contact with social workers or support organizations.
 - Geographic differences validation.

Assess whether the model has been validated across different geographical or regional contexts to ensure external generalizability.

 - Level of geographic stratification: urban vs. rural settings, regions, hospitals, or health districts.

- Environmental and resource-related factors: variations in healthcare infrastructure, resource availability, or population demographics.
- Data heterogeneity: differences in data sources, coding systems, or clinical practices between regions.

1.3.4. *Interoperability – technical compatibility*: Evaluate whether the existing infrastructure (Electronic Health Records (EHR) systems, data formats, APIs) is compatible with the AI system provided by the model developers to ensure smooth integration and functionality within the external validation setting.

1.3.5. *Interoperability – semantic compatibility*: Assess whether the variable definitions, coding systems (e.g., SNOMED CT, ICD-10), and clinical terminologies used at the external validation site are semantically aligned with those in the training dataset.

1.4. Good practices

This section presents a set of recommended practices that may be adopted by model developers prior to external validation. Their adoption is intended to facilitate collaboration between model developers and validators (Local Data Validation Team), enhance transparency, and support the interpretability and reproducibility of results.

However, the extent to which these practices can be applied depends on the model developer's willingness to share information, institutional policies, and applicable confidentiality, commercial, or privacy constraints. Therefore, all recommendations should be interpreted as encouraged but non-mandatory actions, to be adapted to each specific regulatory and organizational context.

1.4.1. *Public code and full methodology documentation*

Where feasible, model developers are encouraged to make available the codebase (e.g., preprocessing scripts, training pipeline, evaluation tools) and the complete data wrangling process (e.g., cleaning, imputation, feature engineering, normalization) used for model development and validation. Public release (e.g., via GitHub or Zenodo) can promote transparency, reproducibility, and peer review.

Nevertheless, this is subject to confidentiality, commercial sensitivity, and privacy risks, which may limit the degree of openness. When full release is not possible, controlled sharing mechanisms (e.g., restricted access or non-disclosure agreements (NDAs)) are recommended to allow traceability and accountability while protecting proprietary or sensitive assets.

1.4.2. *FAIR principles compliance*

Model developers and validators (Local Data Validation Team) are encouraged to report the degree to which their datasets and associated artifacts follow the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Examples of FAIR-compliant actions include providing metadata, using persistent identifiers, specifying licensing terms, and ensuring interoperability with other systems.

Full FAIR implementation may not always be achievable due to regulatory, ethical, or commercial constraints. In such cases, partial adherence—for example, making data findable and accessible under controlled conditions—is still encouraged, along with clear documentation on how access requests can be managed through secure or contractual procedures.

Block 2: Operational Steps for External Validation

This block provides guidance on the operational implementation of external validation. It encompasses the definition and assessment of context-appropriate performance metrics, bias and fairness analyses, and the application of explainability and interpretability techniques to enhance transparency. It also introduces governance mechanisms for setting performance thresholds, defining revalidation triggers, and establishing good practices. Together, these elements ensure a structured, reproducible, and context-sensitive recommended external validation process, aligned with the model's risk classification and intended clinical use.

2.1. Performance metrics across different scenarios

This section focuses on the selection and evaluation of performance metrics during external validation. Model validators (Local Data Validation Team and HTA body) may consider the following guidance when selecting and assessing performance metrics during external validation. Even if model developers optimised the algorithm using a specific metric, this metric may not be suitable for the clinical question or for the characteristics of the external population. Validators should assess whether additional or alternative metrics are needed to reflect model behaviour in a clinically meaningful and fair manner. Adopting a broader set of evaluation metrics can also reduce the risk of overfitting to local data and support generalisation across healthcare settings.

The following categories summarize the main types of performance metrics commonly used in validation, depending on the problem (regression, binary classification or multiclass classification):

- *Regression metrics*
 - Mean Squared Error
 - Mean Absolute Error
 - Determination Coefficient (R^2)
 - Rooted Mean Squared Error
 - Bias (Mean Error)

- *Classification metrics*

Binary classification

- Accuracy
- Recall (sensitivity)
- Specificity
- Precision
- Negative Predictive Value
- F1 Score
- Matthews Correlation Coefficient
- Log Loss (Cross-Entropy Loss)
- AUC-ROC + ROC graph
- AUC-PR + PR Graph

Multi-class classification

- Core Metrics (Accuracy, Balanced Accuracy, Confusion Matrix)
- Macro-Averaged Precision/Recall/F1

- Micro-Averaged Precision/Recall/F1
- Matthews Correlation Coefficient
- Log Loss (Categorical Cross-Entropy)
- AUC-OVR
- AUC-PR

After defining the general metric categories, specific clinical use cases are presented, with example scenarios and the corresponding metrics recommended for evaluation for each of them.

2.1.1. *Regression scenarios*

- *Scenario 1. Prediction of aPTT value after unfractionated heparin administration*

Type of data: Structured tabular clinical data (e.g., lab results, demographics, vitals, medication information)

Context

This scenario involves a regression model that predicts the activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) after an intravenous bolus of unfractionated heparin. The model provides a continuous estimate of coagulation response based on patient-specific variables (baseline coagulation profile, comorbidities, weight, concurrent medications). Because aPTT guides real-time dose titration, prediction accuracy directly affects patient safety.

Clinical Use Case

The model is used to support anticoagulation dose adjustments. Underestimation of aPTT may lead to excessive dosing and bleeding risk, while overestimation may result in insufficient anticoagulation and thrombosis risk. The model must remain accurate across the full aPTT range, particularly near clinically critical thresholds. Evidence shows moderate performance in published ML models (e.g., RMSE \approx 30 s; AUC \approx 0.73 when cast as a categorical task), levels generally insufficient for safe clinical use. Conventional weight-based protocols achieve therapeutic range in \approx 97% of cases within 24 h, offering a benchmark for acceptable clinical accuracy.

Recommended Metrics

- Mean Squared Error (MSE)
- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)
- Bias (Mean Error)

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- RMSE: Ideally $<$ 15–20 seconds, approaching established titration protocol performance.
- Bias: Minimal systematic tendency to under- or over-predict, with particular importance at high-risk aPTT ranges.
- Sensitivity to dangerous extremes (if monitored): Preferably \geq 85–90%.

Validation Challenges

- Differences in population characteristics (comorbidities, baseline coagulation status, medication interactions) may alter model behaviour compared with the development setting.
- Variation in local clinical practices (heparin titration protocols, monitoring frequency, therapeutic targets) can influence calibration and expected error structure.
- Laboratory-related variability (aPTT assay type, reagents, equipment calibration) may introduce systematic shifts in observed outcomes and degrade external validity.

- Clinically consequential errors: even modest under- or over-predictions can lead to bleeding or thrombotic complications, making small performance deficits clinically unacceptable.
- *Scenario 2. Prediction of ICU length of stay*

Type of data: Structured tabular clinical data (physiology, labs, severity scores, comorbidities)

Context

Predicting ICU length of stay (LOS) is a complex regression problem, as LOS is influenced by heterogeneous clinical variables, evolving physiological trajectories, complications, and institutional discharge practices. LOS distributions are typically right-skewed, with many short stays and fewer prolonged ones, making prediction particularly difficult for long-stay patients. Regression models commonly incorporate severity-of-illness scores, organ dysfunction indicators, ventilatory parameters, comorbidity burden, and early physiological trends. In the literature, LOS prediction is considered moderately feasible for short stays but substantially less accurate for longer admissions, where variability increases markedly. Machine learning models often achieve modest improvements over traditional scoring systems, but generalisability remains limited across hospitals.

Clinical Use Case

The model is used to support operational and logistical planning in the ICU, including bed allocation, staffing adjustments, resource anticipation (e.g., ventilators, renal replacement therapy), and downstream coordination with step-down units and wards. While small errors (1–2 days) are generally tolerable, underestimating LOS in high-acuity patients can lead to bed shortages, ICU bottlenecks, or delays in elective admissions, whereas overestimation reduces operational efficiency. Published studies suggest that MAE \approx 1–2 days for short stays and \approx 2 days for longer stays is considered clinically acceptable. Models exhibiting large variance or systematic biases (persistent over- or underestimation) are unsuitable for real-time planning. Thus, predictions must remain stable across demographic and clinical subgroups, preserving utility under fluctuating ICU demand.

Recommended Metrics

- Mean Squared Error (MSE)
- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)
- Bias (Mean Error)

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- MAE/RMSE equivalent: Clinical practice suggests errors \approx 1–2 days are acceptable; RMSE \approx 2 days is considered clinically useful.
- Bias: Mean Error should be close to zero, avoiding systematic over- or under-estimation.
- Error distribution: Large outlier errors should be infrequent, particularly for long LOS cases.

Validation Challenges

- Case-mix differences (severity, diagnoses, ventilation use) may fundamentally change LOS patterns between development and validation sites.
- Local ICU workflow, discharge criteria, and bed-flow policies can alter LOS distributions, affecting calibration.
- LOS is often right-skewed; small errors in short stays but large errors in long-stay patients may be hidden without proper distributional evaluation.

- Operational sensitivity: systematic underestimation may lead to over-crowding, whereas overestimation may produce inefficient bed utilisation.
- *Scenario 3. Prediction of 10-year cardiovascular risk using chest radiographs.*

Type of data: Multimodal data (imaging features extracted from chest radiographs + structured clinical metadata)

Context

This regression scenario combines imaging-derived features from chest radiographs with clinical metadata to estimate the probability of a cardiovascular event over 10 years. The model attempts to extract anatomical or physiological markers—such as mediastinal contours, aortic calcifications, and cardiothoracic ratios—that correlate with long-term cardiovascular risk. Traditional risk scores (Framingham, ACC/AHA Pooled Cohort Equations) rely exclusively on tabular clinical data; adding imaging aims to improve prediction in situations with incomplete clinical data or to capture subclinical disease. External studies demonstrate that radiograph-based risk models can achieve c-statistics around 0.75–0.80, comparable to classical risk equations, though calibration performance varies significantly across populations.

Clinical Use Case

The model is designed to support preventive cardiology, particularly decisions regarding statin initiation or intensification, lifestyle interventions, or referral to specialist care. Clinical guidelines rely on risk thresholds (typically $\geq 10\%$ or $\geq 20\%$ 10-year risk) to inform treatment decisions. Therefore, calibration—especially around these thresholds—is as important as discrimination. Overestimation of risk may expose patients unnecessarily to long-term medication, whereas underestimation may delay preventive therapy in high-risk individuals. Published evidence shows that even small miscalibrations (3–5% absolute deviation) can significantly shift treatment recommendations. Consequently, the model must provide stable, interpretable probabilities across diverse demographic groups, ensuring alignment with established prevention strategies.

Recommended Metrics

- Mean Squared Error (MSE)
- Mean Absolute Error (MAE)
- Bias (Mean Error)

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Discrimination proxy (if available): Comparable to established models (AUC ≈ 0.75 – 0.80).
- Calibration: Predicted risk should match observed risk within a few percentage points across risk deciles; miscalibration near clinical thresholds is unacceptable.
- MAE: Preferably only a few percentage points deviation (< 3 – 5%).
- Bias: Avoid systematic overestimation or underestimation of risk across subgroups.

Validation Challenges

- Differences in imaging protocols, equipment, and radiographic quality may affect extracted features and degrade model performance.
- Clinical characteristics, disease prevalence, and treatment patterns vary by region, affecting risk distributions and calibration.
- Threshold-based decisions amplify the clinical impact of small calibration errors.
- Subgroup effects may emerge (e.g., across sex or age groups), requiring stratified calibration assessment.

- *Scenario 4. Prediction of optimal tuberculosis treatment duration*

Type of data: Structured tabular clinical data + microbiological data (e.g., smear status, culture conversion times, clinical response)

Context

This regression model predicts personalised treatment duration for tuberculosis (TB) based on clinical variables, microbiological conversion patterns, radiological findings, and host factors. TB treatment traditionally follows fixed-duration regimens (e.g., 6 months), and attempts to shorten therapy require extremely robust evidence to avoid relapse or resistance. Clinical trials exploring 4-month regimens have shown that even modest under-treatment increases failure rates. Therefore, modelling therapeutic duration is considered high-risk and must incorporate factors such as bacterial load, smear/culture dynamics, cavitation, and early treatment response. Published machine learning models show variable performance, and their safety depends heavily on avoiding under-prediction.

Clinical Use Case

The model supports personalised therapy decisions to reduce overtreatment toxicity and improve adherence while maintaining cure rates above established clinical standards (>90–95%). Underestimation of required duration carries major clinical consequences: relapse, disease progression, need for re-treatment, and potential emergence of drug resistance. Clinical trials defining non-inferiority margins (~6.6%) provide a benchmark for acceptable deviation from standard regimens. In practice, model-guided recommendations must perform comparably to current fixed-duration protocols or better. Slight overestimation may be tolerated, but underestimation is unacceptable. As a result, the model must incorporate mechanisms or safeguards to detect high-risk profiles requiring extended therapy.

Recommended Metrics

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE)
- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)
- Bias (Mean Error)

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Clinical non-inferiority frame: Cure rates following model-recommended durations should not fall >5–6% below standard therapy benchmarks (~95%).
- MAE: Ideally only a few days to 1–2 weeks; large deviations (≥ 1 month) unacceptable.
- Bias: Systematic under-prediction particularly dangerous; bias should be strongly non-negative.
- Sensitivity for prolonged-treatment cases: High sensitivity required to avoid prematurely short recommendations.

Validation Challenges

- Differences in *M. tuberculosis* strains, resistance patterns, and public health protocols affect treatment length and outcome distributions.
- Local laboratory practices influence culture conversion timing, altering model inputs and expected outputs.
- Variation in adherence and comorbidity burden may degrade generalisability.
- High clinical risk if the model underestimates necessary treatment duration.

2.1.2. *Binary classification scenarios*

- *Scenario 5. Risk Stratification of Severe Events in COVID-19 Patients*

Type of data: Structured tabular clinical data (labs, vitals, comorbidities, oxygenation indices)

Context

This binary classifier predicts which hospitalised COVID-19 patients will experience severe outcomes such as respiratory failure, ICU admission, or death (moderately to highly imbalanced dataset). Inputs typically include vital signs, inflammatory biomarkers, comorbidity burden, oxygenation indices, and radiological findings. The pandemic introduced rapid temporal shifts: new variants, evolving treatment protocols, vaccination effects, and differing hospital capacities—all of which affect model transferability. Published prognostic models span a wide range of performance, with many early models failing external validation due to data drift and cohort heterogeneity.

Clinical Use Case

The model assists clinicians in early triage, escalation planning, and allocation of scarce resources such as ICU beds and ventilators. High sensitivity is crucial to ensure patients at significant risk are not missed, particularly during surges when delays in escalation can be fatal. Literature from validated prognostic models (e.g., ISARIC 4C score) demonstrates that $AUC \approx 0.77\text{--}0.85$ is achievable, with higher thresholds required for safe deployment. Some clinical environments prioritise extremely high sensitivity (>90%), accepting reduced specificity to avoid missing critically ill patients. Performance requirements may tighten for use in emergency departments or low-resource settings.

Recommended Metrics

- Recall (Sensitivity)
- AUC-ROC + ROC curve
- F1 Score
- AUC-PR + PR curve
- Specificity

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Recall (Sensitivity): Preferably $\geq 85\text{--}90\%$ to ensure most severe cases are captured.
- AUC-ROC: ≥ 0.80 to be considered clinically useful.
- AUC-PR: Should exceed baseline prevalence substantially.
- Trade-off: Some reduction in specificity acceptable to prioritise patient safety in triage use.

Validation Challenges

- Epidemic waves generate shifts in patient characteristics, viral variants, and treatment protocols, altering model performance.
- Class imbalance may differ between development and validation settings.
- Calibration drift over time may affect the reliability of probability estimates.
- False negatives may result in missed escalation of care with potentially fatal consequences.

- *Scenario 6. Colorectal Cancer Diagnosis Using Histological Images*

Type of data: Imaging data (digital pathology slides)

Context

This scenario uses a binary classifier applied to digital histopathology slides to distinguish malignant from benign colon biopsy samples (highly imbalanced dataset). High-resolution whole-slide images contain complex morphological patterns requiring models capable of fine-grained feature extraction. Variability in staining, scanners, slice thickness, and preprocessing pipelines makes external validation particularly challenging. Research models have achieved near-expert performance (AUC \approx 0.97–0.99), but their generalisation outside controlled datasets remains uncertain.

Clinical Use Case

The model is primarily intended as a triage tool: to prioritise suspicious slides for expedited review and potentially auto-exclude clearly benign samples. The overwhelming clinical priority is not missing cancer—thus sensitivity and NPV must be extremely high. Studies demonstrate that setting operating thresholds to achieve \approx 99% sensitivity can reduce pathologist workload by \sim 50% without compromising safety. False positives are acceptable to some extent because they simply trigger review rather than omission. Consequently, this is a high-risk use case requiring stringent validation across institutions.

Recommended Metrics

- Specificity
- Precision
- AUC-ROC + ROC curve
- Negative Predictive Value
- Recall (Sensitivity)

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Recall (Sensitivity): Extremely high (\approx 99%), ensuring virtually no cancers are missed.
- NPV: Also extremely high, given its role in ruling out disease.
- AUC-ROC: Values approaching 0.97–0.99 seen in high-performing research models.
- Specificity: Can be moderately relaxed (\geq 90%) to ensure sensitivity trade-off.

Validation Challenges

- Differences in staining techniques, scanners, and slide preparation significantly affect generalisation.
- Local prevalence of malignancy and sampling variation influence predictive values.
- Distribution shift due to different patient populations may degrade performance.
- High clinical risk if even a small number of malignant slides are misclassified as benign.

- *Scenario 7. Hospital Readmission Prediction After Stroke*

Type of data: Structured tabular EHR data (demographics, comorbidities, labs, functional scales)

Context

This binary classification model predicts whether a patient discharged after stroke will be readmitted within a defined timeframe (e.g., 30 days) (moderately imbalanced dataset). Stroke patients represent a clinically heterogeneous population, with readmission influenced by factors such as residual disability, comorbidity burden, caregiver support, complication risk, and access to rehabilitation. Models typically incorporate functional scales (e.g., modified Rankin Scale), laboratory values, imaging features, demographics, and clinical history. Literature reports modest predictive performance due to the multifactorial nature of readmission events.

Clinical Use Case

The model is intended to identify patients who may benefit from intensified follow-up, rehabilitation planning, medication optimisation, or early outpatient interventions. Underprediction (false negatives) may delay necessary care and increase the risk of avoidable complications or mortality. Overprediction (false positives) may misallocate limited follow-up resources. Published models show that balanced sensitivity and specificity ($\approx 70\text{--}80\%$) are often considered clinically acceptable, but higher sensitivity may be prioritised to avoid missing high-risk individuals. The model must also account for local variability in discharge practices, community support availability, and health-system structure.

Recommended Metrics

- Recall (Sensitivity)
- Specificity
- Precision
- Negative Predictive Value
- F1 Score

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Sensitivity: Ideally $\geq 70\text{--}80\%$, given the goal of identifying patients needing close follow-up.
- Specificity: $\geq 70\text{--}80\%$ to avoid excessive unnecessary resource allocation.
- F1 Score: Should reflect balanced performance in imbalanced datasets; desirable $\geq 0.60\text{--}0.70$.
- NPV: Important to ensure safe ruling-out of low-risk patients.

Validation Challenges

- Hospital-level differences in discharge practices, community support, and rehabilitation availability affect readmission rates.
- Coding quality and completeness vary widely, influencing predictor reliability.
- Functional status measures may not be available or comparable across sites.
- Class imbalance differs by institution, affecting calibration and threshold selection.

- *Scenario 8. Screening for Rare Genetic Diseases*

Type of data: Structured tabular clinical data + sometimes genomic markers

Context

This binary classifier predicts whether a patient may have a very rare genetic condition (prevalence $<0.05\%$, extremely imbalanced dataset). Extreme class imbalance poses substantial challenges, as most patients are true negatives. Models integrate clinical phenotypes, laboratory markers, diagnostic codes, and potentially genomic or biochemical indicators. Because rare diseases often present with nonspecific symptoms, models can easily overfit to artefacts or spurious correlations in the development dataset.

Clinical Use Case

The model functions as a triage tool to help clinicians identify which patients warrant confirmatory genetic testing. False negatives may delay diagnosis of severe hereditary conditions, while false positives may overwhelm specialist services or trigger unnecessary, expensive testing. In the literature, screening models for rare diseases aim for very high sensitivity (often $>90\%$) alongside improved precision compared with baseline prevalence. However, even large relative gains in precision may still yield low PPVs due to rarity.

Therefore, models must be carefully calibrated and validated with local prevalence estimates and subgroup analyses.

Recommended Metrics

- Precision
- Recall (Sensitivity)
- AUC-PR + PR curve
- AUC-ROC + ROC curve
- Specificity

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Precision: Must far exceed prevalence; even 10–20× improvement may still yield modest PPV.
- Recall: Ideally $\geq 90\%$ given high clinical consequences of missing true positives.
- AUC-PR: More informative than ROC due to extreme class imbalance; should safely exceed baseline prevalence curve.
- Specificity: High specificity ($>95\%$) needed to avoid excessive unnecessary confirmatory testing.

Validation Challenges

- Extreme rarity of outcomes leads to unstable estimates and high sensitivity to local prevalence shifts.
- Data availability for the rare disease phenotype may be limited in local institutions.
- Genomic or biochemical markers may differ depending on available laboratory processes.
- False positives burden limited specialist resources; false negatives delay diagnosis of serious conditions.

2.1.3. *Multi-class classification scenarios*

- *Scenario 9. Glioma Subtype Classification*

Type of data: Imaging (MRI) + histopathology + molecular markers (where available)

Context

This multiclass ordinal model differentiates glioma subtypes or grades (e.g., II, III, IV) based on imaging, histopathology, and, where available, molecular signatures (moderately imbalanced dataset). Gliomas exhibit substantial intratumoral and interobserver variability, and diagnostic accuracy varies even among expert neuropathologists ($\approx 85\text{--}90\%$ agreement). Machine learning approaches attempt to integrate imaging phenotypes (MR sequences), texture features, tumour shape, and deep-learning representations to improve consistency and speed.

Clinical Use Case

The classifier supports treatment selection, prognosis estimation, enrolment into clinical trials, and communication with patients. Misclassification between adjacent grades may be acceptable in some contexts, but misclassifying a low-grade tumour as glioblastoma (or vice versa) has major therapeutic implications. Literature suggests that specialist-level accuracy ($\sim 85\text{--}90\%$) is a reasonable minimum requirement. Furthermore, ordinal awareness is crucial: the model should rarely confuse extreme categories. Balanced accuracy and MCC are particularly informative given uneven class distributions.

Recommended Metrics

- Macro-Averaged Precision/Recall/F1
- AUC-OVR
- Accuracy / Balanced Accuracy / Confusion Matrix
- Log Loss (Categorical Cross-Entropy)
- Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Accuracy / Balanced Accuracy: Ideally $\geq 80\text{--}85\%$; upper benchmark \approx specialist-level accuracy.
- MCC: High MCC desirable to ensure robust multiclass agreement.
- Error structure: Misclassification across non-adjacent ordinal categories should be extremely rare.
- Log Loss: Should reflect well-calibrated class probabilities.

Validation Challenges

- MRI protocols vary significantly by scanner and institution, affecting image-derived features.
- Histopathology interpretation standards differ internationally.
- Molecular profiles included in training may not be available locally.
- Class imbalance and rare subtypes may destabilise performance estimates.

- *Scenario 10. Classification of Adverse Drug Reaction Types*

Type of data: Structured EHR data (labs, vitals, medication exposure) \pm clinical notes (if used)

Context

This multiclass nominal classifier categorises potential adverse drug reactions (ADR) (e.g., gastrointestinal, neurological, dermatological, none). ADR prediction relies on clinical variables, laboratory values, demographics, comorbidities, and medication exposure patterns (highly imbalanced dataset). Real-world ADR data are highly heterogeneous and often incomplete, with under-reporting being common. Published models typically achieve moderate discrimination (AUC $\approx 0.77\text{--}0.81$), reflecting the difficulty of reliably detecting ADR patterns.

Clinical Use Case

The model aims to support clinicians in anticipating likely ADRs prior to treatment initiation or when evaluating unexplained patient symptoms. Accurate categorisation may guide preventive measures, monitoring intensity, or treatment adaptation. False negatives may miss early signs of severe ADRs, while false positives may lead to unnecessary changes in therapy, increased monitoring, or patient anxiety. A minimum level of balanced accuracy ($>70\text{--}75\%$) and reasonable macro-F1 ($>0.60\text{--}0.70$) is typically expected before relying on the model clinically, particularly to ensure minority ADR types are not systematically overlooked.

Recommended Metrics

- Macro-Averaged Precision/Recall/F1
- Accuracy / Balanced Accuracy / Confusion Matrix
- AUC-OVR
- Log Loss (Categorical Cross-Entropy)
- AUC-PR

Illustrative Minimum Acceptable Performance Thresholds

- Balanced Accuracy: $\geq 70\text{--}75\%$ to ensure performance across rare and common ADR classes.
- Macro-F1: Ideally $\geq 0.60\text{--}0.70$, ensuring minority classes are adequately predicted.
- AUC-OVR: ≥ 0.80 to reflect reasonable discrimination for each ADR category.
- Log Loss: Should reflect consistent and well-calibrated probability outputs.

Validation Challenges

- ADR documentation varies greatly across institutions; coding inconsistencies reduce model transferability.
- Rare ADR classes may be poorly represented in local datasets.
- Medication formularies differ between hospitals and countries, altering exposure distributions.
- Misclassification may lead either to unnecessary treatment interruption or failure to detect a harmful reaction.

2.2. Bias and fairness analysis

This section focuses on the identification and assessment of biases that may influence model performance, reliability, and fairness across population subgroups during external validation.

At this stage, the goal is to evaluate and document existing disparities, not to modify or retrain the model, since the algorithm has already been developed and approved by the model developers. Findings from this assessment should inform decisions about the model's suitability for local deployment and guide risk-proportionate mitigation or monitoring strategies.

2.2.1. *Data collection bias*

Biases introduced during data collection (e.g., sampling, temporal, aggregation, measurement, or representation bias) should be carefully examined to determine whether differences in data capture or population structure could explain observed performance shifts in the validation dataset.

Documenting these sources helps interpret whether observed inequities arise from contextual differences rather than algorithmic flaws.

2.2.2. *Algorithmic bias*

Review potential algorithm-level biases inherited from the development process, such as optimization criteria that favour majority classes, feature selection bias, or evaluation bias.

Although model validators (Local Data Validation Team) cannot alter the algorithm itself, understanding these mechanisms supports a more accurate interpretation of subgroup performance and facilitates transparent reporting.

2.2.3. *Fairness analysis*

Maintaining fairness across patient groups is a key consideration before deployment, particularly in clinical contexts with high impact on safety or access. Model validators (Local Data Validation Team) should compute fairness metrics—such as demographic parity, equal opportunity difference, subgroup accuracy, false-positive/negative rate differences, or disparate impact—to identify systematic disparities between subgroups (See item 1.3.3).

The purpose is to assess whether observed disparities remain within acceptable bounds for the model’s risk class. Thresholds should be interpreted as context-dependent reference ranges, not rigid pass/fail rules.

Table 2. Recommended fairness disparity threshold, according to AI-CDSS risk class

Model Risk Class	Recommended Fairness Disparity Threshold	Interpretation
Class I – Low-risk	≤ 10 % disparity across subgroups	Acceptable if disparities are minor and clinically negligible
Class IIa – Moderate-risk	≤ 7 %	Recommend additional monitoring if exceeding this range
Class IIb – High-risk	≤ 5 %	Close scrutiny and justification required; bias monitoring recommended
Class III – Very high-risk / life-critical	≤ 3–5 %	Any larger disparity should trigger detailed review before deployment

These thresholds are intended to guide validators (HTA body) in contextualizing subgroup differences and documenting equity considerations transparently. If a model exceeds the suggested thresholds, it does not imply automatic rejection, but rather the need for explicit justification, clinical risk assessment, and enhanced post-deployment monitoring.

2.3. Explainability and interpretability

This section focuses on the assessment of explainability and interpretability to help model validators (Local Data Validation Team and HTA body), clinicians, and multidisciplinary teams understand how models generate predictions. Explainability techniques in AI (XAI) are essential in external validation to assess whether a previously developed ML/DL model behaves consistently and in a clinically plausible manner when applied to new, local data. These techniques support the examination of the model’s decision logic and the verification of its plausibility in the local context. This understanding strengthens transparency and safe clinical use, and helps identify potential model limitations in real-world validation settings (e.g., misuse, overconfidence).

2.3.1. Explainability techniques

Explainability vs Interpretability:

Although often used interchangeably, explainability and interpretability serve distinct but complementary purposes:

- Explainability refers to the ability to describe how input features influence the model’s predictions. Commonly used approaches include model-derived effect estimates such as odds ratios in logistic regression and equivalent effect measures in other parametric methods, together with model-agnostic techniques (e.g., SHAP, LIME, Partial Dependence Plots, Individual Conditional Expectation, Counterfactual Instances) and deep-learning-specific tools (e.g., Grad-CAM, DeepLIFT, Activation Maximization, Integrated Gradients). These methods allow

validators to examine feature attribution, evaluate the stability of explanations under controlled perturbations, and identify potential undue dependencies or early indicators of bias.

- Interpretability focuses on the clinical and biological plausibility of the model's reasoning — examining whether its behaviour aligns with established medical knowledge and domain understanding. When appropriate, this includes assessing the model's underlying causal assumptions and exploring potential cause-and-effect relationships through causal inference methods, to ensure that the associations detected reflect clinically meaningful mechanisms rather than spurious correlations.

Global vs Local Explanations:

- Global explanations summarize how the model behaves across the entire external dataset. They provide insights into which features generally influence predictions and help detect shifts in model reliance compared to the original development context. Examples include SHAP summary plots, feature permutation importance, or Partial Dependence Plots (PDP).
- Local explanations focus on single predictions, identifying what drove the model's output for an individual case. These are particularly useful in reviewing high-risk or misclassified instances. Local tools include LIME, SHAP individual force plots, or counterfactual examples.

Model-Specific vs Model-Agnostic Methods:

- Model-specific methods leverage the internal structure of the model. For instance, Grad-CAM uses internal activations and gradients in CNNs to highlight image regions that influenced the prediction. Integrated Gradients and DeepLIFT produce attribution scores based on path-integrated gradients or reference-based decompositions and are suitable for differentiable deep learning architectures.
- Model-agnostic methods operate independently of the model type. LIME fits local surrogate models to approximate the decision boundary around a specific instance, while SHAP applies game-theoretic principles to assign contribution scores to each feature at both local and global levels. These methods are applicable even when the underlying model architecture is not accessible during external validation.

Intrinsic vs Post-hoc Interpretability:

- Intrinsic interpretability applies when the model itself is transparent (e.g., decision trees, sparse linear models). Reviewers can directly examine feature weights or decision rules.
- Post-hoc interpretability is required for complex or black-box models (deep neural nets, ensembles). Explanations are generated after training to approximate the model's reasoning. In external validation, these methods are critical to determine if the model remains interpretable in a new context.

2.3.2. *Criteria for validating explainability and interpretability*

When validating a model externally, explainability should be used to evaluate how well the model's reasoning transfers to the new dataset. Each of the following criteria addresses a distinct aspect of this goal:

- Plausibility of cause–effect associations: Examine whether the features identified as influential by explainability methods align with established clinical knowledge or plausible physiological mechanisms. If a mortality model highlights age, oxygen saturation, or inflammatory markers, these would typically support plausibility. Conversely, reliance on metadata or device IDs may indicate spurious associations.
- Stability of feature importance: Assess whether key feature attributions remain consistent across different patient subgroups, time periods, or repeated runs. Variability may suggest instability or sensitivity to local data characteristics. Consistent feature rankings across samples increase confidence in the model’s robustness.
- Sensitivity to perturbations: Validate that minor, clinically irrelevant changes in input data do not significantly alter predictions or explanations. Conversely, clinically meaningful changes (e.g., an increase in creatinine) should result in expected changes in risk estimates and corresponding shifts in feature attributions.
- Bias and undue dependence detection: Identify whether the model disproportionately relies on variables that serve as proxies for protected attributes (e.g., ethnicity, insurance type). Use stratified explanations to inspect whether model behaviour changes across subgroups. Inconsistent logic may indicate dataset shift or fairness concerns.
- Clinical alignment: Ensure that explanations correspond to clinical reasoning. Domain experts should be able to interpret the outputs without requiring access to model internals. Any divergences between the model’s behaviour and clinical plausibility should prompt further scrutiny or adjustment.

2.3.3. *Explainability review and interpretation*

To ensure transparency and facilitate multidisciplinary evaluation, explanation results should be documented and reviewed with structured criteria.

- Methodology disclosure: Clearly specify which explainability methods were applied, their scope (global or local), and whether they are model-agnostic or model-specific. Include any relevant configuration details (e.g., SHAP baseline values, number of LIME samples, Grad-CAM target layer).
- Bias and fairness analysis: Use explainability to identify differential model behaviour across key subgroups. Analyse whether certain features dominate predictions in one group but not another, and whether any variables raise fairness or equity concerns. Document whether corrective steps were taken.
- Checks for consistency and stability: Evaluate whether similar patients receive similar explanations. Repeat explainability analyses on different subsamples or with alternative methods to ensure consistency. For example, compare SHAP to LIME outputs, or repeat Grad-CAM using different convolutional layers.
- Summary of key findings from explanations: Describe what the explanations revealed about the model’s behaviour on the external dataset. Highlight top features, deviations from expected logic, and any changes compared to internal validation. Visual representations (e.g., summary plots, heatmaps, ICE curves) should accompany textual summaries.

- Expert involvement in validation: Explanations should be reviewed by clinical and technical experts jointly. Clinicians should assess whether the model's reasoning is clinically sound, while technical reviewers ensure methodological correctness. Divergences from expected patterns should be discussed collaboratively to distinguish between true clinical heterogeneity and potential model failure.
- Limitations and uncertainties. Make clear that explanations indicate model reliance, not clinical causality. Highlight methodological limitations (e.g., instability of LIME, lack of ground truth in saliency maps). Encourage cautious interpretation, especially when explanations appear clinically plausible but are derived from flawed or biased training data.

2.3.4. *Example of XAI use cases*

To ensure transparency and facilitate multidisciplinary evaluation, explanation results should be documented and reviewed with structured criteria.

- ICU mortality prediction: SHAP analysis on local ICU data revealed consistent reliance on fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂), Glasgow comma scale or age (11). Minor differences in feature order prompted subgroup-specific inspection.
- Pneumonia detection from chest X-rays: Grad-CAM visualisations confirmed model attention on lung infiltrates. However, in some cases, attention maps included image corners or text labels, suggesting overfitting to training artefacts (12).
- Stroke prediction: The LIME technique successfully provided instance-specific local explanations, illuminating the features that either boosted the stroke prediction or demonstrated minimal influence, indicating insufficient predictive power. Furthermore, in ambiguous or borderline predictions, LIME occasionally assigned significant weight to proxy variables such as residence type or work type. Since these factors possess little direct clinical relevance for stroke, the model's reliance on them suggests the need for cautious interpretation and clinical validation of its outputs (13).
- Prediction of cardiovascular disease: Global feature ranking can be used to identify an optimal subset of input variables by deprioritizing features with limited predictive contribution (e.g., gender or height). This may help simplify the model structure, improve explainability, and support more robust performance during external validation (14).
- Readmission risk for diabetes patients: can be used to identify patterns in heavily weighted features, generate interpretable outputs, explain interactions and relationships between features, and enhance overall model transparency (15).

2.4. Governance of performance criteria and revalidation triggers

This section focuses on the governance principles that guide when and how additional validation actions should be taken. It defines the minimum acceptable performance thresholds for external validation and identifies the key triggers that may warrant new validation cycles. Together, these elements help model validators (HTA body) establish structured, risk-based processes to ensure that AI-CDSS remain reliable, fair, and clinically relevant across evolving healthcare environments. The

recommendations provided here are intended as flexible guidance rather than prescriptive rules, allowing adaptation to local governance structures, data maturity, and model risk levels.

2.4.1. *Recommended minimum performance thresholds*

Given the potential mismatch between development and deployment populations, performance during external validation should be interpreted using absolute, risk-stratified performance floors derived from the local dataset rather than relative drops from training results. These thresholds provide recommended minimum acceptable values for the primary validation metrics, adapted to the model's risk class and clinical use case:

Table 3. Suggested minimum absolute performance metrics, according to AI-CDSS risk class

Model Risk Class	Suggested Minimum Absolute Performance Metric*
Class I – Low-risk	≥ 75 %
Class IIa – Moderate-risk	≥ 80 %
Class IIb – High-risk	≥ 85 %
Class III – Very high-risk / life-critical	≥ 85-90 %

*These thresholds apply primarily to classification models, where performance metrics are percentage-based. For regression models, acceptable performance should be defined using error-based metrics (e.g., RMSE, MAE, bias), depending on the clinical context, outcome range, and tolerance to prediction error.

Performance thresholds for classification scenarios should also be interpreted in relation to the metric's clinical meaning. Not all metrics require the same level of stringency, for example:

- In scenarios where false negatives carry severe clinical risk (e.g., cancer detection), metrics like recall should be high (≥ 95-99%).
- When datasets are imbalanced, a balanced or F1 score ≥ 80% may indicate sufficient performance if fairness and calibration are preserved.

Model validators (HTA body) should always apply methodological criteria and interpret results in light of:

- Sample size, verifying statistical robustness and confidence intervals;
- Clinical context, ensuring that the primary evaluation metric is appropriate for the model's intended use case;
- Model risk level, selecting operating thresholds that minimize expected clinical harm; and
- Fairness metrics, monitoring subgroup performance disparities.

2.4.2. *Triggers for initiating additional validation cycles*

This item refers to events that may occur either during the external validation process or after clinical deployment as part of ongoing monitoring. These triggers capture potential changes that can arise between the start of the validation period and the point when validation metrics are finalized, or later during real-world use. Such events may affect data integrity, model behaviour, or clinical relevance, and therefore require an additional validation cycle to reassess performance, safety, and fairness.

This framework also recognises that a significant time gap may exist between model validation and final deployment (see Item 3.1.1 Frequency of periodic local validation cycles). During monitoring, these triggers should be aligned with the local monitoring infrastructure and institutional governance procedures.

Triggers are categorized according to their priority and potential impact on model reliability and clinical safety. Many of these events can be considered routine checks and therefore systematically analysed during the periodic local validation cycles described in 3.1.1.

High priority

- 2.4.2.1. *Data distribution changes (data shift/drift/updating)*: Changes in the statistical distribution of input data, patient characteristics, or population composition compared to the training data or previous local validation cycles (e.g., major demographic or epidemiological shifts).
- 2.4.2.2. *Concept drift*: Changes in the underlying relationship between input variables and the target outcome (e.g., a pandemic, emergence of a new clinical syndrome, evolving disease definitions).
- 2.4.2.3. *Model performance degradation (performance drift)*: Noticeable drops, unexpected improvements, or significant variance in key performance metrics over time across the overall local validation cohort or general population. Unexpected improvements should be also investigated as potential anomalies or data artefacts, not only performance drops.
- 2.4.2.4. *Performance Disparities within specific populations (bias/fairness degradation)*: Significant fluctuations or unacceptable performance within predefined high-risk clinical use cases or specific patient subgroups (e.g., age, sex, ethnicity), even if overall performance seems stable (See items 1.1.15 and 1.2.5), in order to assess the model's fairness and equity.

Medium priority

- 2.4.2.5. *Changes in clinical protocols or guidelines*: Modifications in medical guidelines, diagnostic criteria, or treatment standards that could affect the model's relevance or applicability.
- 2.4.2.6. *Changes in workflows or interoperability resources*: Alterations in data sources, electronic health record (EHR) systems, data formats, interoperability assets, or clinical workflows that could affect interoperability, data flow, or model integration within the healthcare environment.

2.4.2.7. *Feedback and concerns from end-users*: Direct input or reports from clinicians, patients, or other healthcare professionals regarding unexpected model outputs, errors, or usability issues.

Low priority

2.4.2.8. *Regulatory or compliance changes*: New AI-specific laws, policies, or ethical guidelines requiring reassessment of model performance, safety, or deployment.

2.4.2.9. *Risk reassessment*: Periodic or ad hoc re-evaluation of risks associated with continued model use, conducted by the validation governance team or institutional oversight committee, and triggered by new events, emerging evidence, or observed performance or safety issues.

2.5. Good practices

This section provides recommended practices to promote transparency, collaboration, reproducibility, and clinical relevance during the external validation process. These actions are recommendations to strengthen methodological rigor and stakeholder communication throughout validation. By fostering clear documentation, shared access to validation tools, and structured reporting, these practices aim to support trustworthy, auditable, and clinically meaningful validation outcomes.

2.5.1. *Public code and full methodology documentation*

Model validators (Local Data Validation Team) are encouraged to make validation-related code (e.g., preprocessing scripts, evaluation pipelines) and methodological documentation accessible when feasible. This supports transparency, reproducibility, and peer review, aligning with FAIR and open science principles. When public release is not possible due to confidentiality, commercial sensitivity, or privacy concerns, controlled access mechanisms (e.g., NDAs, restricted repositories) should be used to maintain traceability and accountability (See *Item 1.4.1 for detailed guidance and examples*).

2.5.2. *Version control, collaborative documentation, and audit trails*

Maintain rigorous documentation of local validation datasets, code versions, and decisions made throughout the validation process. Collaborative tools (e.g., shared repositories, wikis, or version-controlled documents) should be used to ensure real-time tracking of performance results, model behaviour, and methodological updates. This promotes consistency, transparency, and readiness for audit or regulatory review (See *Items 1.4.1–1.4.2 for complementary FAIR principles and documentation recommendations*).

2.5.3. *Definition and assessment of clinical utility*

Establish clear definitions of the model's intended clinical use case and how its utility will be assessed during external validation. This includes defining relevant decision thresholds, considering clinical workflows, and evaluating the balance of benefits and harms in the target setting (e.g., using metrics like Net Benefit or Expected Cost).

2.5.4. *Stakeholder communication and reporting*

Establish clear, ongoing reporting mechanisms to keep all relevant stakeholders (e.g., clinicians, technical teams, governance bodies) informed of validation progress, findings, and emerging issues, including defined protocols for communicating unexpected model behaviour or safety concerns to oversight teams.

ANNEX - Block 3: Post-Deployment Best Practices for Validation and Monitoring

This annex to the VALID-AI guideline includes a set of items that extend beyond the current scope of the main framework. It has been developed to provide additional recommendations for post-deployment best practices, focusing on aspects of ongoing validation, monitoring, and governance once AI-based CDSS are implemented in real-world healthcare settings.

This final block focuses on ensuring that validated AI-CDSS remain reliable, fair, and clinically meaningful after deployment. It provides recommendations on how to govern, monitor, and continuously assess model performance, equity, and safety over time. The section also broadly addresses the ethical, regulatory, and operational dimensions involved in sustaining AI systems in clinical practice, including fairness reporting, stakeholder engagement, open science, and long-term governance.

These practices are not prescriptive but serve as guiding principles to promote trustworthy and adaptive AI adoption, ensuring that validated models continue to deliver clinical value while maintaining public trust, accountability, and alignment with societal and institutional standards.

3.1. Governance of validation cycles

3.1.1. Frequency of periodic local validation cycles

After deployment, periodic local validation cycles are recommended to reassess model performance, safety, and fairness under real-world conditions. The suggested frequencies (Table 4) are illustrative guidelines, adaptable to each institution's data availability, infrastructure, and model risk class. These post-deployment validations form part of a continuous monitoring framework, helping ensure that the AI-CDSS remains reliable, clinically relevant, and aligned with evolving healthcare practices.

Table 4. Recommended frequency of periodic local validation cycles, according to AI-CDSS risk class

Class	Description	Examples	Validation Frequency
I	Low-risk models	Simple risk scores, administrative alerts with minimal patient impact	Annually
IIa	Moderate-risk models with potential clinical impact	Diagnostic aids, treatment recommendation tools with moderate consequences	Quarterly
IIb	High-risk models affecting significant clinical decisions	Models guiding critical treatment choices or major diagnoses	Monthly
III	Very high-risk, life-critical models	Models influencing intensive care, emergency interventions, surgical decisions	Weekly

3.1.2. Number of local validation iterations for stability

The recommended number of validation iterations required to confirm model stability after deployment is summarized in Table 5. These values should be interpreted as context-dependent recommendations, not strict requirements, and may be adapted according to model risk class, data maturity, and local governance capacity. The goal is to establish sufficient evidence of stable model behaviour over time, recognizing that higher-risk models may benefit from more frequent or extended monitoring.

Even when stability has been demonstrated, specific triggers defined in Item 2.4.2 (Triggers for initiating additional validation cycles) may warrant the initiation of a new validation cycle to reassess performance, fairness, or safety in response to demographic, contextual or clinical changes.

Table 5. Recommended number of local validation iterations after deployment, according to AI-CDSS risk class

Class	Description	Examples	Number of local validation iterations after deployment
I	Low-risk models	Simple risk scores, administrative alerts with minimal patient impact	3 stable cycles
IIa	Moderate-risk models with potential clinical impact	Diagnostic aids, treatment recommendation tools with moderate consequences	4 stable cycles
IIb	High-risk models affecting significant clinical decisions	Models guiding critical treatment choices or major diagnoses	>5 cycles, until stability is achieved
III	Very high-risk, life-critical models	Models influencing intensive care, emergency interventions, surgical decisions	>5 cycles, until stability is achieved

3.2. Discrimination analysis, fairness reporting, and ethical alignment

This section covers the disclosing of fairness limitations and subgroup performance variability after external validation. Proactively considering these aspects helps ensure that AI systems remain aligned with patient needs, societal values, and ethical principles over time.

- 3.2.1. *Ongoing fairness reporting*: It is important that models continue to track subgroup-level performance over time, maintain transparency about fairness-related limitations, and disclose findings through appropriate documentation (e.g., public reports, audit logs, clinical guidance notes).
- 3.2.2. *Discrimination disclosure*: Models should include warnings when performance is lower in specific populations (e.g., older adults, minorities), to inform clinical use and support equitable decision-making.
- 3.2.3. *Promoting ethical use*: In addition to bias and fairness, models should be evaluated for their alignment with broader ethical principles, such as patient autonomy, accountability, and transparency regarding the AI's role in clinical decision-making.

3.3. Stakeholder and end-user involvement

This section highlights the involvement of multidisciplinary teams throughout the post-validation, deployment, and implementation phases to ensure responsible and clinically meaningful AI integration. Their diverse perspectives enhance the robustness of evaluation processes, promote fairness, help identify potential risks or blind spots, and ultimately increase the societal and clinical relevance of AI models.

- 3.3.1. *Multidisciplinary team leadership*: Validation processes should be led by multidisciplinary teams that integrate technical, clinical, regulatory, and ethical expertise, and involve broader stakeholder groups.
- 3.3.2. *Inclusion of diverse backgrounds*: It's essential that these teams and stakeholder groups also reflect diverse backgrounds and lived experiences (e.g., gender, race, geographic origin) to enhance the robustness of evaluation, promote fairness, and identify potential blind spots related to various population segments.
- 3.3.3. *End-user feedback*: Collecting structured feedback from end-users post-validation is critical to refining the model, addressing implementation barriers, and ensuring that it meets practical clinical needs.

3.4. Regulatory and open science considerations

This section promotes responsible AI by ensuring that model use after external validation aligns with regulatory requirements, fosters scientific transparency, and adheres to open science principles.

- 3.4.1. *Compliance with evolving regulatory frameworks* should be monitored continuously post-validation to ensure ongoing alignment with legal and ethical standards, particularly in high-risk clinical settings.
- 3.4.2. *Open science principles*, including the public sharing of code, validation datasets, and detailed documentation, support transparency, reproducibility, and collaborative improvement of AI models. These principles should align with the TRIPOD-AI and EQUATOR Network guidelines, which emphasize detailed reporting on data sharing (availability, repositories, access conditions, and accompanying data dictionaries) and code sharing (public analytical code, documentation, and computing environment). Following these open science standards, together with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), ensures that data, code, and documentation are transparent, traceable, and reusable across healthcare settings while respecting confidentiality and ethical constraints.

3.5. Post-deployment monitoring and long-term adoption

This section focuses on ensuring that AI models remain effective, safe, and clinically relevant after deployment. It highlights the continuous monitoring of real-world use, long-term operational sustainability, and the need to adapt to evolving clinical practices, user behaviour, technological changes, and equity concerns.

- 3.5.1. *Monitoring of real-world use and performance:* Track how frequently and appropriately the model is used by clinical staff, assess its impact on health outcomes, safety, and equity, and employ automated tools to monitor key indicators in real time (e.g., model/data drift, KPIs, user satisfaction, fairness metrics).
- 3.5.2. *Education and behavioural strategies:* Provide targeted training on AI tools and apply behavioural techniques to support appropriate, consistent, and responsible use by healthcare professionals, thereby facilitating successful integration and adoption.
- 3.5.3. *Evaluation of real-world clinical impact:* Use patient-reported outcomes (e.g., EQ-5D) and clinical feedback to assess quality of life and detect when further validation or recalibration may be needed due to changes in clinical context or technology.
- 3.5.4. *Operational long-term sustainability:* Regularly evaluate whether the model remains cost-effective, practical to implement, and aligned with available organisational resources, ensuring its continued viability over time.

4 Conclusion

D4.2 has produced VALID-AI (VALidation of Local Indicators in the pre-Deployment phase of AI-CDSS), a consensus-based guideline (2-Round Delphi methodology) for the external and local validation of AI-CDSS in the post-regulatory, pre-deployment phase. VALID-AI provides a structured framework to ensure that AI-CDSS are evaluated with real-world data prior to adoption in clinical practice, addressing requirements of robustness, fairness, transparency, accountability, and clinical relevance.

The guideline is organised into three blocks: pre-validation requirements, which establish the necessary documentation, cohort comparisons and good practices; operational steps, which define methodological rigor in metric selection, bias and fairness analysis, explainability and interpretability, and governance of performance criteria; and post-validation practices (Annex to VALID-AI), which encompass governance of validation cycles, fairness reporting, stakeholder communication, regulatory alignment, and strategies for sustainable deployment. By bringing together model developers and independent validators, VALID-AI promotes transparency, comparability and reproducibility, ensuring that AI-CDSS perform reliably across diverse local populations. In line with the EQUATOR guidelines, a virtual Consensus Meeting was held on October 6th, 2025, during which the final guideline content and item wording were agreed upon to ensure that the definitive version is both robust and comprehensive. This updated D4.2 therefore represents a near-final version of the guideline, ready for submission to a high-impact journal.

The framework aligns conceptually with the requirements set out in the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) and the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act), including principles of ethical and trustworthy AI, robustness, transparency, accountability, and the classification of AI-CDSS according to their risk level under the AI Act, recognising that systems may range from lower-risk models with minimal patient impact to high-risk applications subject to strict regulatory oversight. VALID-AI therefore complements existing European and international frameworks by translating high-level regulatory principles into practical methodological guidance for external validation. As VALID-AI applies specifically in the post-regulatory, pre-deployment phase, it assumes that AI-CDSS have already fulfilled the requirements of European regulatory frameworks, including the AI Act and MDR/IVDR. The added value of VALID-AI lies in bridging the remaining gap between regulatory approval and clinical use by providing a structured methodology for external validation with local RWD. This ensures that algorithms proven safe and effective in regulatory processes are also robust, fair, and clinically relevant in the specific healthcare contexts where they will be deployed.

Further integration and consolidation of VALID-AI within the broader ASSESS-DHT framework will take place in upcoming deliverables, notably D4.6 Manual for the assessment of digital health technologies (Consolidated framework with all final criteria & DHT-type-specialist pathways, workflows, and guides), which will unify the work across tasks in WP4 and incorporate feedback from pilots and case studies, while also ensuring alignment with the aforementioned European AI regulations. In parallel, other tasks of the project will continue to address complementary life-cycle aspects such as data quality, privacy, cybersecurity, interoperability and metadata labelling, in line with the requirements of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), ensuring overall coherence in the final ASSESS-DHT framework.

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ANNEX I: Glossary of terms

The concepts are organized alphabetically to facilitate their search. Some broad definitions include a specific list of related items.

- **Accuracy:** Proportion of correct predictions. Accuracy measures the percentage of all predictions (both positive and negative) that are correct. In imbalanced data sets, it can be misleading if it is a ruling class. Example: In a model that predicts whether a patient has a chronic disease, if the model correctly predicts 950 out of 1000 patients, the accuracy would be 95%. However, if only 50 patients actually have the disease, this metric would not correctly reflect the model's performance in detecting the disease.
- **Algorithmic Bias:** Refers to systematic and unfair outcomes resulting from the way an algorithm processes data, learns patterns, or is evaluated. These biases can stem from flawed design choices, such as inappropriate optimization functions that prioritize overall accuracy over fairness, or biased feature selection that inadvertently excludes or misrepresents important information for certain groups. They can also arise from unintended interactions between model components and data characteristics. One of the most common forms of algorithmic bias is:
 - Evaluation Bias: Occurs when the metrics, datasets, or procedures used to assess an AI model systematically favour certain subgroups or outcomes, leading to misleading conclusions about the model's fairness or generalizability.

Example: A model predicting hospital readmissions is evaluated only on patients with private insurance, showing high accuracy. However, when deployed, it performs poorly for publicly insured patients due to different care pathways and documentation practices. The evaluation process failed to represent the target population, introducing evaluation bias.
- **Algorithm family type:** Refers to the general category or class of machine learning algorithms used for prediction tasks, which share similar underlying principles or approaches to model the relationship between input (independent) variables and an output (dependent) variable. These are typically grouped into:
 - Regression models: Predict continuous numerical outcomes.

Examples: Linear regression, ridge regression, lasso regression.

Healthcare example: Predicting a patient's blood pressure based on their medical history, age, and other risk factors.
 - Classification models: Predict discrete categories or class labels.

Examples: Logistic regression, decision trees, random forests, gradient boosting, neural networks.

Healthcare example: Using logistic regression to estimate the probability of postoperative complications based on factors like age, surgery type, and clinical status.

- **AUC (Area Under the Curve):** A measure of the performance of a classification model. It represents the area under a curve that plots the trade-off between true positive and false positive rates. A larger area indicates better performance in distinguishing between positive and negative classes. A value of 0.5 indicates random performance, while a value of 1 indicates perfect discrimination. Example: For a model that predicts the probability of relapse in cancer patients, a high value indicates that the model is very effective at distinguishing between patients who will relapse and those who will not.
- **AUC-OVR (Area Under the Curve-One vs. Rest):** Performance measure for multiclass problems. AUC-OVR measures a model's ability to distinguish between a particular class and all other classes. An AUC is calculated for each class against the others, and then averaged. Example: In a cancer type classification model (for example, lung, breast, and skin), the AUC-OVR can show the model's ability to distinguish between each cancer type and the other types.
- **AUC-PR (Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve):** A performance metric for classification models, especially useful for imbalanced datasets. The precision-recall (PR) curve plots precision (the proportion of true positives among predicted positives) against recall (the proportion of true positives identified out of all actual positives) at various classification thresholds. The AUC-PR summarizes the model's ability to maintain both high precision and high recall. Example: In a model predicting a rare infectious disease, the AUC-PR reflects how well the model identifies positive cases without producing too many false positives, even when positive cases are much less frequent than negative ones.
- **AUC-ROC (Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve):** A performance metric for classification models that measures their ability to distinguish between classes. The ROC curve plots the true positive rate (recall) against the false positive rate ($1 - \text{specificity}$) at various classification thresholds. The AUC-ROC summarizes the model's overall discriminative ability. It is widely used for evaluating classification models, although it may be less informative than the AUC-PR in highly imbalanced datasets. Example: In a model predicting heart attacks, the AUC-ROC shows how well the model distinguishes between patients who will and will not experience a heart attack, balancing sensitivity (recall) and the rate of false alarms.
- **AU-ROC + ROC graph:** Quantifies a model's ability to distinguish between two classes using the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve. The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUROC) measures how well the model separates positive from negative cases (e.g., sick vs. non-sick). The ROC curve plots the true positive rate (recall) against the false positive rate ($1 - \text{specificity}$) at various classification thresholds. An AUROC of 1.0 indicates perfect discrimination, while 0.5 suggests no better performance than random chance.
- **Balanced accuracy:** Average of recall and specificity. Balanced accuracy adjusts the overall accuracy of a model by equally considering both recall (true positive rate) and specificity (true negative rate), making it especially useful for imbalanced datasets. Example: In a cancer detection model, if the recall is 80% and the specificity is 70%, the balanced accuracy would be 75%, offering a more balanced assessment of the model's performance.
- **Balancing methods:** Techniques used to address class imbalance in datasets, which can negatively affect the performance of machine learning models, particularly in classification

tasks. These methods aim to ensure that the model does not become biased toward the majority class. Examples:

- Oversampling (e.g., SMOTE – Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique): Generates synthetic data points for the minority class.
 - Undersampling: Reduces the number of examples from the majority class.
 - Hybrid methods: Combine oversampling and undersampling to achieve better balance.
 - Example in healthcare: Applying SMOTE to balance a dataset with far fewer patients diagnosed with cardiovascular disease than without, in order to improve the model’s ability to detect high-risk patients.
- **Behavioural techniques:** Strategies used to influence or modify individual or group behaviour in order to achieve specific goals. In the context of AI-based AI-CDSS, behavioural techniques aim to promote the appropriate and responsible use of these tools by clinicians and other end-users. These may include education, prompts, feedback, and incentives, helping to support adoption, overcome resistance, and ensure effective integration into clinical workflows.
 - **Bias (Mean Error):** A regression metric that calculates the average of the prediction errors (predicted value minus actual value). It indicates the systematic tendency of a model to consistently over-predict or under-predict the target variable. A value close to zero indicates less bias, while a positive value suggests consistent over-prediction and a negative value suggests consistent under-prediction. Example: In a model predicting blood glucose levels, a Mean Error of +10 mg/dL would indicate that the model consistently overestimates glucose by 10 mg/dL on average. This systematic over-prediction (bias) could lead to clinical decisions based on inaccurately high glucose readings.
 - **Bias Management Framework:** A comprehensive process encompassing the identification, measurement, mitigation, and monitoring of bias throughout the development and validation of predictive models. This involves detecting potential sources of bias, identifying vulnerable populations, defining fairness objectives, selecting appropriate metrics, and engaging interdisciplinary teams to ensure that bias mitigation is integrated from the outset. The strategy should also specify roles, responsibilities, and documentation practices to support transparency, accountability, and equity. The Bias Management Framework can be broken down into four key components:
 - **Identification:** Involves detecting potential sources of bias, including human bias, data collection bias, and algorithmic bias (see individual entries in the dictionary). This step is critical to understanding where unfairness may originate and how it may affect model outcomes.
 - **Measurement:** Requires the use of fairness metrics (see Fairness Metrics entry) to quantify disparities across population subgroups. Model performance should be evaluated using disaggregated metrics by key characteristics such as age, sex, or ethnicity.
 - **Mitigation:** Refers to the application of methods to reduce or eliminate bias during model development. This may include fairness-aware data preprocessing, balancing techniques such as stratified sampling or oversampling of underrepresented groups (see Balancing Techniques entry), and—where appropriate—controlling for or excluding sensitive variables (e.g., race or gender). Fairness-enhancing modelling

strategies such as Fair Representation, Demographic Parity, Equal Opportunity, or specific architectures like DeepFair and Fair Linear Regression can also be used to minimize algorithmic bias.

- **Monitoring:** Bias should be continually reassessed during prospective external validation and post-authorization deployment. This step helps ensure that model performance does not degrade in clinical practice and that fairness is maintained over time and across real-world settings, especially as data distributions shift or as the model encounters new populations.
- **Brier Score:** A metric that measures the accuracy of probabilistic predictions in binary classification models. It calculates the mean squared difference between predicted probabilities and the actual binary outcomes (0 or 1). A lower Brier Score indicates better calibration and accuracy of the predicted probabilities. Example: If a model predicts an 80% probability (0.8) that a patient will develop diabetes, and the patient indeed develops diabetes (actual outcome = 1), the error is small, resulting in a low Brier Score.
- **Calibration:** The process of adjusting a model's predicted probabilities to better reflect observed outcomes. A well-calibrated model provides probability estimates that closely match the actual frequencies of events. Calibration can be applied globally or tailored to specific subpopulations if prediction accuracy varies across groups. For example, calibrating a cardiovascular risk model ensures that patients predicted to have a 20% chance of a heart attack actually experience the event about 20% of the time.
- **Calibration Graph (or Calibration Plot):** A visual tool that compares predicted probabilities with observed event frequencies to assess how well a model is calibrated. The graph plots predicted probabilities against actual outcomes, ideally aligning points along the identity line ($y = x$). For example, a calibration plot for a hospital mortality prediction model shows whether patients predicted to have a 30% mortality risk actually experience a 30% mortality rate.
- **Causal Inference/Understanding:** A field of study and set of statistical and mathematical methods focused on establishing cause-and-effect relationships from data, moving beyond mere correlations. Its aim is to understand why outcomes occur and what would happen under hypothetical interventions, which is crucial for robust decision-making in complex and high-stakes domains like healthcare. Common causal inference methods include:
 - **Do-calculus:** A formal framework developed by Judea Pearl that enables reasoning about interventions using causal graphs. It allows researchers to determine whether a causal effect can be estimated from observational data and how.
 - **Propensity Score Matching (PSM):** A technique to balance treated and untreated groups by matching individuals with similar covariate profiles, simulating the conditions of a randomized experiment.
 - **Inverse Probability Weighting (IPW):** A method that reweights samples to create a pseudo-population in which treatment assignment is independent of covariates.
 - **Instrumental Variables (IVs):** Used when there is unmeasured confounding; relies on variables that affect the treatment but not the outcome directly.
 - **Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (TMLE):** A semi-parametric method that combines machine learning with causal inference for more robust estimation of causal effects.

- Causal Forests: An extension of random forests that estimates heterogeneous treatment effects across subpopulations.
- Structural Causal Models (SCMs): Mathematical models that explicitly represent causal mechanisms using equations and directed graphs.
- **Classification**: A type of supervised machine learning technique that involves assigning a label or category to data based on its characteristics. It predicts the class of new, unseen data using a model trained on previously labelled examples. Classification is used to categorize data into discrete groups. Example: Classifying medical images to diagnose lung cancer based on identifiable shapes and textures.
- **Concept drift**: Occurs when the relationship between input features and the target outcome changes over time, affecting model reliability. Example: If treatment protocols change, a model trained on past data may no longer predict current outcomes accurately.
- **Confusion matrix**: A summary of the performance of a classification model. A confusion matrix displays the number of true positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and false negatives (FN), helping to assess how well the model distinguishes between classes. Example: In a model predicting diabetes, the confusion matrix might show that, out of 100 patients, 70 were correctly identified as diabetic (TP), 20 were incorrectly identified as diabetic (FP), 5 were incorrectly classified as non-diabetic (FN), and 5 were correctly classified as non-diabetic (TN).
- **Correlation**: A statistical measure that describes the strength and direction of a relationship between two variables. Correlation values range from -1 to 1 . A positive correlation indicates that as one variable increases, the other tends to increase; a negative correlation indicates the opposite. A value close to 0 suggests no linear relationship. Example: In healthcare, there may be a positive correlation between age and blood pressure, meaning that blood pressure tends to increase as patients get older.
- **Data collection bias**: Refers to systematic errors introduced during the process of gathering data, which can distort model training and reduce generalizability. It can occur due to how, when, where, or from whom the data are collected. Examples of human bias are:
 - Measurement bias: Arises when there are systematic inaccuracies or inconsistencies in how variables are measured or recorded, leading to distorted model inputs.

Example: In EHR-based models for predicting acute kidney injury, serum creatinine values may be recorded inconsistently across hospitals due to variations in laboratory calibration methods or testing frequency. These discrepancies can introduce measurement bias, causing the model to misinterpret normal physiological variation as pathological, and potentially affecting risk prediction accuracy across sites.
 - Sampling bias: Occurs when the dataset used to train a model is not representative of the target population, often due to non-random or selective inclusion of data. This can compromise the generalizability and fairness of model predictions.

Example: A predictive model for diagnosing diabetic retinopathy is trained exclusively on imaging data from high-income urban centres. As a result, the model may underperform on patients from rural or lower-income regions, where access to

healthcare and diagnostic equipment is limited. This sampling bias can lead to lower diagnostic accuracy and reduced clinical utility in underserved populations.

- **Representation Bias**: Arises when certain subgroups are underrepresented, misrepresented, or overrepresented within a dataset, leading the model to perform unevenly across populations. This often reflects historical and structural inequalities embedded in healthcare data collection and documentation.

Example: An AI model trained on EHR data may exhibit representation bias when it overrepresents male patients and underrepresents female patients, especially in conditions like heart disease. This imbalance stems from historical bias in medical research, which has traditionally focused on male populations, and cognitive bias among clinicians that leads to underdiagnosis in women. As a result, the model may be less accurate in detecting heart disease in female patients.

- **Aggregation Bias**: Occurs when models are trained on heterogeneous data from multiple subgroups, but fail to account for important differences between them—resulting in a model that performs well on average, but poorly for specific subpopulations.

Example: A risk prediction model trained on aggregated EHR data from multiple institutions might show high accuracy overall but mask performance disparities. For instance, the model may perform well for male patients and poorly for female patients, but the aggregate performance appears acceptable, obscuring subpopulation harm and potentially leading to inequitable clinical outcomes.

- **Temporal Bias**: Arises when models are trained on data from one time period but applied to data from a different period, during which clinical practices, patient populations, or disease patterns may have changed—leading to reduced model performance.

Example: A model trained on pre-pandemic EHR data for respiratory illnesses may underperform when applied to post-pandemic data due to the impact of COVID-19. Changes in clinical practice (e.g., revised treatment protocols, triage criteria), disease prevalence, and patient behaviour (e.g., increased use of telemedicine, delayed care-seeking) introduce temporal shifts that reduce the model's generalizability and reliability in the new context.

- **Emergent Bias**: Arises when a model behaves differently or produces unintended consequences when deployed in a real-world environment, due to changes in context, user interactions, or evolving system dynamics that were not anticipated during training.

Example: An AI system for hospital triage performs well in controlled trials but, after deployment, clinicians begin to over-rely on its recommendations. This leads to reduced clinical judgment and unintended patient harm, an emergent bias caused by changes in user behaviour and workflow not captured during development.

- **Omitted Variable Bias**: Occurs when relevant variables influencing the outcome are missing from the dataset or model, causing inaccurate or misleading associations with the variables that are included.

Example: A mortality prediction model developed using EHR data may omit key social determinants of health, such as housing instability or access to care, which are not routinely documented. As a result, the model may wrongly attribute risk to proxy variables like race or insurance status, reinforcing structural inequities in healthcare delivery.

- **Data dictionary:** A comprehensive tool that provides definitions, descriptions, and metadata for data elements within a database system. It includes detailed information such as field names, descriptions, data types, length and time window specifications, allowed values, units of measurement, data resolution, and applicable standards (e.g., ICD-10). It also outlines constraints, relationships between data elements, data sources, and the origin of the data, serving as a reference to ensure consistency, accuracy, and clarity in data usage and management.
- **Data drift:** Refers to gradual, non-stationary changes in the statistical distribution of a model's input variables over time. These changes can arise from natural population evolution, shifts in data collection methods, or technological improvements, potentially leading to a decline in model performance if not adapted. It doesn't necessarily imply a change in the fundamental relationship between inputs and the outcome. Example: A model predicting blood glucose may drift as population diet trends subtly shift over years.
- **Data preprocessing:** The set of procedures applied to raw data before model development to ensure quality, consistency, and suitability for analysis. In the context of AI in healthcare, data preprocessing includes steps such as handling missing data (e.g., imputation methods), identifying and removing outliers, normalizing or scaling numerical features, encoding categorical variables (e.g., one-hot or ordinal encoding), temporal alignment of clinical events, and harmonizing variable definitions across datasets. Proper preprocessing is essential to avoid introducing bias, ensure reproducibility, and enhance model performance and generalizability.
- **Data shift:** This is a broader, more general term encompassing any difference in data distribution between two datasets—such as a model's training set and a new validation or deployment set. It can include various types of changes like covariate shift (change in input variable distribution), concept shift (change in the relationship between inputs and outcome), or prior probability shift (change in outcome prevalence). Data shift can be sudden or gradual and significantly impacts a model's ability to generalize to new environments. Example: Applying a model trained on urban patients to a rural hospital, where demographics are notably different, represents a data shift.
- **Data updating:** The process of incorporating new, real-world data into an existing dataset or model pipeline, often requiring re-validation or re-training to maintain accuracy. Example: An AI model predicting patient readmission rates is regularly updated with the latest six months of electronic health record (EHR) data. This new data helps keep the model current with clinical practices, but it also means the model's performance must be re-evaluated.
- **Dependent variable:** The outcome or target that is influenced by one or more independent variables. In statistical analysis and machine learning, it is the variable being predicted—the output of the model. Example: In a study on the effect of medication dosage on blood pressure,

blood pressure is the dependent variable, as it changes in response to the treatment (independent variable).

- **Effectiveness:** Refers to the extent to which a treatment or intervention produces the desired beneficial outcomes under real-world conditions. Unlike efficacy, which is assessed in controlled clinical trials, effectiveness accounts for factors such as patient adherence, variations in clinical practice, comorbidities, and other real-life influences that can affect performance in routine care.
- **Expected Calibration Error (ECE):** A metric used to assess the calibration of probabilistic classification models. It represents a weighted average of the absolute difference between predicted probabilities and observed outcome frequencies across predefined probability bins. ECE quantifies how closely the predicted probabilities align with actual outcomes, with lower values indicating better calibration. Example: In a disease classification model, if predictions consistently assign a 70% probability of disease but only 60% of those cases actually have the disease, the ECE captures this mismatch.
- **Explainability:** The extent to which the internal mechanics of a machine learning or deep learning model can be understood and interpreted by humans. Explainability tools help clarify how models make decisions, increasing trust, transparency, and accountability—especially in high-stakes domains like healthcare. To better understand and interpret model predictions, various explainability methods have been developed. These can be broadly grouped into general techniques—applicable to both machine learning and deep learning models—and methods specifically designed for deep learning architectures:

General Explainability Methods (ML and DL)

- Feature importance: Measures the relative influence of each input feature on the model's predictions. It helps identify which variables are most relevant for decision-making. Example: In a diabetes prediction model, "blood glucose level" may have high importance, indicating it plays a key role in assessing diabetes risk.
- SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations): A game-theory-based method that assigns each feature a contribution value to explain individual predictions, ensuring fairness and consistency across models. Example: If a model predicts a high risk of heart disease, SHAP can show how much each characteristic (such as high cholesterol or hypertension) contributes to this high prediction.
- LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations): Builds simple, interpretable models around individual predictions to approximate the behaviour of complex models in a local neighbourhood.
- PDP (Partial Dependence Plots): Graphs that show the average effect of one or two features on a model's predictions by varying those features while keeping others constant. Example: In a breast cancer prediction model, a PDP could show how cancer risk changes with patient age.
- ICE (Individual Conditional Expectation plots): Plots how changes in a feature affect the model's prediction for individual instances, highlighting variability across cases.
- Counterfactual Instances: What-if scenarios that show how small changes to input features would lead to different predictions. Example: How would changing a patient's age or gender affect a cardiovascular risk prediction?

Deep Learning–Specific Explainability Methods

- Grad-CAM (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping): Visual method that highlights image regions (or other input areas) that contribute most to a convolutional neural network’s (CNN) decision, enhancing interpretability in visual models. Useful in medical imaging for understanding diagnostic reasoning.
 - DeepLIFT (Deep Learning Important FeaTures): Attributes changes in model output to input features by comparing neuron activations relative to a reference input, offering faster and clearer attributions.
 - Activation Maximization: Visualizes the input patterns that most strongly activate specific neurons or layers within a neural network. This method helps interpret the features the model has learned to recognize. For example, in a convolutional neural network trained to classify medical images for pneumonia detection, activation maximization can highlight the specific areas of the image that most strongly influence the model’s diagnosis.
 - Integrated Gradients: Computes feature importance by averaging gradients as input values move from a baseline to the actual input, offering robust explanations across models.
- **External and Contextual Factors**: Real-world conditions outside the model’s control that may influence performance, such as hospital workflows, population differences, or technology availability.
 - **F1 Score**: A performance metric for classification models, especially useful when dealing with imbalanced classes. It is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a single score that balances both false positives and false negatives. Precision measures the proportion of true positives among predicted positives, while recall measures the proportion of true positives among actual positives. Example: In a model designed to detect a rare disease, overall accuracy may be misleading due to the low prevalence of positive cases. A high F1 Score would indicate that the model is effectively identifying true cases while limiting false alarms.
 - **Fairness Metrics**: Quantitative indicators used to assess whether an AI model performs equitably across subgroups defined by sensitive attributes (e.g., race, sex, age). These metrics help identify disparities in performance and support bias mitigation strategies. Below are commonly used fairness metrics in healthcare AI:
 - False Positive Rate by Group: Measures how often individuals from each subgroup receive an incorrect positive prediction. Disparities may indicate that the model disproportionately flags certain groups as high risk without justification.
 - False Negative Rate by Group: Evaluates how frequently individuals from each subgroup are incorrectly predicted as negative. High false negative rates in a group can lead to missed diagnoses or delayed treatment.
 - Subgroup accuracy: Assesses whether the overall predictive accuracy (i.e., correct classifications) varies between groups. A significant gap may reveal that the model serves some populations better than others.
 - Equal Opportunity Difference: Quantifies the difference in true positive rates between subgroups. It ensures that individuals who qualify for a positive outcome

(e.g., disease detection) are equally likely to be correctly identified, regardless of group.

- Equalized Odds: Extends equal opportunity by requiring both true positive and false positive rates to be similar across subgroups, aiming for consistent model behaviour in both correct and incorrect predictions.
 - Statistical Parity Difference (a.k.a. Demographic Parity): Compares the overall rate of positive predictions between groups, regardless of true outcomes. Disparities suggest one group is more likely to receive favourable predictions.
 - Disparate Impact: Calculates the ratio of positive outcomes between groups. A value below 0.8 (the “80% rule”) may indicate potential discrimination, especially in legal or compliance contexts.
 - Odds Ratio: Assesses how the odds of receiving a positive outcome differ between groups. A value significantly different from 1 indicates potential bias in decision-making.
 - Theil Index: An inequality measure borrowed from economics. It quantifies how unequally model outputs are distributed across groups. Higher values indicate more disparity.
 - Calibration by Group: Evaluates whether predicted probabilities align with observed outcomes within each group. A model may be well-calibrated overall but systematically over- or under-estimate risk in specific subgroups.
- **Human bias**: Systematic distortions in perception, judgment, or behaviour arising from cognitive, cultural, or social factors. Examples of human bias are:

- Cognitive bias: Systematic errors in thinking or decision-making that arise from mental shortcuts, heuristics, or personal experiences. These biases can unconsciously influence how humans interpret information, label data, or make clinical judgments.

Example: A clinician overestimates the likelihood of a heart attack in male patients presenting with chest pain, based on prior experience. This leads to underdiagnosis in women. If this pattern is reflected in the training data, the model may learn to associate male gender with higher cardiac risk, perpetuating the bias.

- Historical bias: Bias that arises when data reflect long-standing inequalities, stereotypes, or discriminatory practices embedded in historical decisions or systems. Even accurate data can encode past injustices that distort current predictions or recommendations.

Example: An AI system provides different diagnostic and treatment recommendations based on the patient's race or gender, even when clinical presentations are identical. This reflects entrenched disparities in historical medical data and may lead to inequitable care.

- Population bias: Bias that emerges when the training population does not accurately represent the broader or target population, leading to models that perform poorly or unfairly across underrepresented groups.

Example: A health AI model trained on prescription data shows higher pain medication usage among men. This stems from population bias, as the training data

reflect prescribing practices where men are more frequently given strong analgesics. The model may then misinterpret this as evidence that male patients experience more severe pain, overlooking sociocultural factors that influence how pain is reported and treated in women.

- Social bias: arises when societal inequalities—such as those related to language, income, or education—affect how data are generated, collected, or interpreted, leading to unfair outcomes for certain groups.

Example: A predictive model for emergency room readmission is trained on clinical data where physicians have systematically documented more comprehensive notes for English-speaking or higher-income patients. These socially driven disparities in documentation quality may lead to better model performance for advantaged groups, reducing accuracy and fairness for underrepresented or marginalized populations.

- Behavioural bias: Occurs when the behaviour of individuals—patients, clinicians, or other stakeholders—influences the data collected, often in systematic ways that reflect existing inequalities or assumptions.

Example: A health monitoring app is used to predict diabetes risk based on user-reported lifestyle data. However, users with healthier behaviours are more likely to consistently input accurate data, while others may underreport unhealthy habits such as poor diet or lack of exercise. This discrepancy introduces bias into the dataset, potentially skewing model predictions toward healthier populations and reducing performance for those at higher risk.

- Content production bias: Occurs when the way information is recorded or expressed systematically varies across different groups or settings, introducing discrepancies in the data that models learn from.

Example: In clinical NLP applications, content production bias can arise when clinical notes use different lexical or semantic patterns depending on the patient's gender, ethnicity, or social background. For instance, female patients may be more frequently described using subjective terms such as “emotional” or “anxious,” while male patients receive more objective descriptors. Additionally, physicians and nurses often differ in how they document clinical encounters—physicians tend to emphasize diagnostic reasoning, whereas nurses focus more on symptom progression and patient behaviour. These inconsistencies can lead NLP models to encode biased or uneven representations of patient populations.

- **Importance of the problem/potential impact**: Refers to the clinical, societal, or operational relevance of the issue that a model, intervention, or study aims to address. It reflects the extent to which solving the problem could improve outcomes, reduce harm, increase efficiency, or guide better decision-making. Highlighting the importance and potential impact helps justify the need for innovation, data-driven approaches, or resource allocation. Example: Early identification of sepsis is critical because timely treatment with antibiotics and fluids can significantly reduce mortality. A predictive model that detects sepsis risk earlier than current clinical practices could lead to faster interventions and save lives.

- **Inclusion/exclusion criteria:** Refers to the predefined set of characteristics used to determine which subjects or data points are eligible or ineligible for inclusion in a study or analysis. These criteria help ensure the study population is appropriate and relevant for addressing the research question, improving the validity and generalizability of the results.
- **Independent/input variables:** Variables that are manipulated or controlled in a study to assess their effect on the dependent variable. They represent factors believed to influence the outcome of an experiment or analysis. Example: In a diet and health study, independent variables could include the type of diet (e.g., vegetarian, Mediterranean), physical activity level, and alcohol consumption, which are analysed to determine their impact on body weight (the dependent variable).
- **Interoperability:** The ability of clinical models and systems to effectively integrate and function within different healthcare environments by ensuring compatibility at both technical and semantic levels. Interoperability is crucial for the successful adoption and reliable performance of AI models across diverse clinical settings.
 - **Technical Interoperability:** Refers to the compatibility between the AI system and the existing technical infrastructure, such as electronic health record (EHR) systems, data formats, and application programming interfaces (APIs). It ensures smooth integration and operational functionality within the local healthcare environment.
 - **Semantic Interoperability:** Involves alignment in the meaning and interpretation of data, including variable definitions, coding standards (e.g., SNOMED CT, ICD-10), and clinical terminologies. This ensures that the data used by the model in different settings are consistent and comparable, preserving the accuracy and relevance of predictions.
- **Interpretability:** Refers to how well a human can understand the reasoning behind a model's predictions or behaviour. It's a broader concept than explainability, encompassing both inherent model transparency (e.g., Decision Trees and Linear Regression are more interpretable than Random Forests or Convolutional Neural Networks) and the insights gained from explanation methods. Beyond just showing input-output influence (associative explanations), interpretability also involves understanding underlying causal relationships and assessing model behaviour under hypothetical interventions, which is essential in high-stakes fields like healthcare.
- **Local population:** Refers to the real-world patient data collected from the specific hospital or healthcare institutions where the algorithm is intended to be deployed. This data is essential for validating and evaluating AI-driven decision support systems to ensure their effectiveness, reliability, and applicability within the particular local clinical context.
- **Log-Loss (or Cross-Entropy Loss):** A performance metric used primarily in probabilistic classification models that measures the accuracy of predicted probabilities. It quantifies the difference between predicted probabilities and actual outcomes, penalizing confident but incorrect predictions more heavily. A lower Log-Loss value indicates better model performance. Example: In a disease diagnosis model, if the model predicts a 0.99 probability for an incorrect diagnosis, the Log-Loss will be high, reflecting a severe error in prediction.

- **Macro-Averaged Precision/Recall/F1:** Metrics used in multi-class classification models where precision, recall, and F1 score are calculated independently for each class and then averaged equally across all classes. This approach treats each class with equal importance, regardless of its size or prevalence. Example: In a disease type classification model, precision, recall, and F1 score are computed for each disease category individually and then averaged, providing a balanced assessment of performance across all disease types, independent of their frequency.
- **Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC):** A single, balanced metric that assesses the quality of binary (or multiclass) classifications, especially useful for imbalanced datasets. It considers all four confusion matrix values (True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives, False Negatives) and provides a correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted binary classifications. MCC ranges from -1 (total disagreement) to +1 (perfect prediction), with 0 indicating random prediction. A higher MCC value indicates better model performance. Example: In a rare disease screening, a model might have high accuracy due to many true negatives. However, MCC would offer a more realistic, lower score by balancing the impact of all correct and incorrect predictions, particularly useful when false positives or false negatives have significant clinical implications.
- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** A performance metric used for regression models that measures the average magnitude of errors between predicted and actual values, without considering their direction. MAE calculates the mean of the absolute differences between predictions and true values. A lower MAE indicates better model performance. Example: In a model predicting hospital length of stay for critically ill patients, a low MAE means the predicted stay durations closely match the actual hospitalization days, while a high MAE indicates larger discrepancies.
- **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** A performance metric used for regression models that calculates the average of the squared differences between predicted and actual values. Squaring the errors penalizes larger errors more heavily. A lower MSE indicates higher model accuracy. Example: In a model estimating patients' average blood pressure, a low MSE shows the predictions are generally close to real measurements, whereas a high MSE indicates large prediction errors.
- **Micro-Averaged Precision/Recall/F1:** These metrics are calculated by aggregating the total true positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and false negatives (FN) across all classes, then computing precision, recall, and F1 score from these totals. This approach gives more weight to larger classes. Micro-averaging is commonly used in multi-class classification models. Example: In a medical test result classification model with multiple disease categories, the micro-averaged precision, recall, and F1 score consider all test results collectively, providing an overall performance metric that favours the most prevalent classes.
- **Mitigation plans:** Strategic frameworks or documents that define proactive measures to identify, address, and manage potential risks—such as bias, data drift, and ethical concerns—throughout the stages of model development, validation, and deployment. These plans help ensure the reliability, fairness, and safety of AI systems in real-world applications.
- **Model/Performance drift:** Refers to the gradual decline in a model's predictive performance over time caused by changes in input data distribution, clinical practices, or user behaviour.

Continuous monitoring and periodic model retraining are essential to maintain accuracy and reliability in real-world settings.

- **Negative Predictive Value (NPV):** A performance metric used in binary classification models, particularly in medical testing, that indicates the probability that a person truly does not have a condition given a negative test result. It reflects how reliable a negative prediction is. Example: in a COVID-19 screening model, if the test predicts a negative result, the NPV tells us the likelihood that the individual is truly COVID-negative. A high NPV means that negative results can be trusted with greater confidence.
- **Nursing homes:** Residential care facilities that provide long-term medical and physical assistance, as well as structured opportunities for social support through activities, events, and communal living. Within the framework of Social Determinants of Health (SDH), nursing homes represent a key setting for assessing social support. Variability in the quality and availability of such support can influence mental health, immune function, and treatment adherence—factors that may ultimately affect health outcomes and equity across populations.
- **Open science practices:** A set of principles and practices aimed at making scientific research more transparent, accessible, and reproducible. This includes the open availability of study data, analysis code, research protocols, and publications to allow for independent review, replication, and reuse by the broader scientific community. Open science promotes collaboration, reduces duplication of effort, and enhances trust in research findings by ensuring that all aspects of the research process are openly shared and verifiable.
- **Performance metrics:** Metrics obtained from an AI model include recall, specificity, precision, and the area under the ROC curve (AUC-ROC), among others (definitions of these concepts can be found elsewhere in this dictionary). These metrics evaluate the model's predictive performance by measuring its ability to correctly identify positive and negative cases. Example: Evaluating an early sepsis detection model in the ICU using these metrics to assess its diagnostic accuracy and clinical utility.
- **Pre-deployment:** Refers to the phase or set of processes conducted prior to the actual deployment of a system, application, or feature into a production or end-user clinical environment. In the context of AI-based Clinical Decision Support Systems (AI-CDSS), this phase occurs after regulatory approval (e.g., FDA, CE mark) but before integration into local clinical workflows. It includes tasks such as external validation using local Real-World Data (RWD), performance assessment in specific populations, workflow integration planning, and evaluation of contextual factors that may affect the system's utility or safety.
- **Precision (Positive Predictive Value or PPV):** A performance metric used in binary classification models, particularly in medical testing, that indicates the probability that a person truly has a condition given a positive test result. It reflects how reliable a positive prediction is. Example: In a COVID-19 screening model, if the test predicts a positive result, the PPV tells us the likelihood that the individual is truly COVID-positive. A high PPV means that positive results can be trusted with greater confidence.
- **Prediction threshold:** The value at which a model's output (e.g., probability or score) is converted into a binary or categorical decision, such as classifying a patient as high-risk. In

healthcare AI, setting an appropriate prediction threshold is critical to aligning model outputs with clinical decision-making needs, balancing sensitivity and specificity, and ensuring safety. Thresholds should be tailored to the local context, considering factors such as prevalence, resource availability, and the potential impact of false positives and false negatives.

- **R² (Coefficient of Determination):** Measures the proportion of variability in the dependent variable that is explained by the model. Commonly used in linear regression, R² indicates how well the predicted values fit the actual values. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 means the model explains all variability and 0 means it explains none. Example: If we are predicting annual income based on education level, an R² of 0.75 means that 75% of the variation in income is explained by education level.
- **Real-time Monitoring of Model Performance:** Continuous tracking of key performance metrics (e.g., precision, recall, AUC-ROC, F1 score) during live deployment to promptly detect performance degradation, data drift, or other issues affecting the model's effectiveness in clinical practice.
- **Recall (True Positive Rate, TPR):** Also known as sensitivity, this is a performance metric used in classification models that measures the proportion of true positive cases correctly identified out of all actual positive cases. Recall reflects the model's ability to detect positive instances and is especially important in contexts where missing positive cases has serious consequences. Example: In a breast cancer detection model, if there are 100 actual cancer cases and the model correctly identifies 90 of them, the recall is 90%, indicating the model effectively captures most cancer cases.
- **Research question:** A clearly defined, focused question that guides a biomedical research study. It specifies the population, intervention or exposure, comparison, and outcome, and helps determine the study design and methodology. A well-formulated research question addresses a gap in knowledge and aims to generate evidence to inform clinical practice or scientific understanding. Example: What is the effect of early administration of antibiotics compared to standard care on mortality rates in critically ill patients with sepsis in the intensive care unit?
- **Risk assessment:** A systematic process of identifying, analysing, and evaluating potential risks associated with the deployment of medical AI models or devices. This includes technical, clinical, and ethical considerations to ensure patient safety and model effectiveness. For medical devices in Europe, risk assessment is a mandatory step to obtain CE marking under the Medical Device Regulation (MDR 2017/745). It involves identifying possible harms, assessing their severity and likelihood, and implementing strategies to mitigate these risks throughout the device's lifecycle, including during external validation cycles to ensure continued safe and effective performance in the clinical setting.
- **Risk classes:** Under the Medical Device Regulation (MDR 2017/745), AI models used in clinical decision-making may be classified into four risk classes, depending on their intended use, impact on health, and potential consequences of failure. This classification determines the depth of validation, monitoring, and regulatory scrutiny required, making risk assessment a central step in external validation and deployment.
 - **Class I (Low risk):** Models with minimal impact on diagnosis or treatment. Example: Symptom checkers used to guide clinical action.

- Class IIa (Moderate risk): Models that provide support but are not solely relied upon for clinical decisions. Example: Tools suggesting diagnostic options that require clinician confirmation.
 - Class IIb (High risk): Models that may inform or drive clinical decisions directly in serious conditions. Example: AI tools that recommend cancer therapies.
 - Class III (Very high risk): Models whose failure could result in death or irreversible deterioration. Example: AI systems used in critical care to drive urgent interventions without oversight.
- **RMSE (Rooted Mean Squared Error)**: A performance metric used in regression models to measure the average magnitude of prediction errors. It is calculated as the square root of the mean of the squared differences between predicted and actual values. RMSE provides an interpretable error value in the same units as the predicted outcome, making it useful for assessing how well a model fits the data. Lower RMSE values indicate better predictive accuracy. Example: In a clinical model predicting the length of stay (LOS) in the ICU, an RMSE of 1.5 days would mean that, on average, the model's predictions deviate from the actual LOS by 1.5 days. This helps assess how reliable the model is for hospital resource planning.
 - **Social Determinants of Health (SDH)**: The non-medical factors that influence health outcomes. These include the conditions in which people are born, grow, live, work, and age, such as education, income, employment, housing, food security, social support, and access to healthcare. Understanding and incorporating SDH into healthcare decisions is essential to address health disparities and ensure equitable implementation of AI-CDSS.
 - **Small Anonymized Dataset Used for Training**: A reduced and de-identified version of the training dataset, typically used for demonstration, reproducibility, or regulatory purposes. It should include a summary of the dataset's origin (e.g., hospital, registry), size (e.g., number of patients and variables), and the anonymization methods applied to protect patient privacy (e.g., data masking, suppression, generalization) in accordance with legal and ethical standards.
 - **Specificity (True Negative Rate)**: A performance metric used in classification models that measures the proportion of true negative cases correctly identified out of all actual negative cases. Specificity reflects the model's ability to correctly identify individuals who do not have a particular condition. High specificity means the model accurately excludes those without the condition, minimizing false positives. Example: In a disease screening model, high specificity indicates that healthy individuals are rarely misclassified as having the disease.
 - **Stress-testing**: A rigorous evaluation process designed to assess the performance, safety, and reliability of an AI model under extreme, rare, or challenging clinical scenarios that push the model beyond typical operating conditions. Stress-testing helps identify potential failure points, limitations, or risks in real-world use, ensuring the model remains robust and safe across diverse and high-risk situations.
 - **Table of baseline characteristics (aka Table 1)**: A summary table that presents the baseline characteristics of the study population, typically stratified by exposure groups, treatment arms, or outcome categories. It is commonly used in biomedical research to describe the distribution of key demographic, clinical, and social variables across cohorts, such as age, sex, comorbidities, or socioeconomic indicators. Table 1 helps assess the comparability between groups and

provides context for interpreting results. It also offers insight into potential sources of confounding, selection bias, and measurement error, making it essential for evaluating internal validity.

- **Target population:** The group of patients or individuals for whom the AI model is intended to be used in clinical practice. This includes the demographic, clinical, and contextual characteristics (e.g., age, condition, care setting) that define the scope of applicability of the model.
- **Train/Test/Validation Splits:** Refers to how the available dataset is divided into three distinct subsets during model development. This division is essential for building robust and unbiased models. For example, if a dataset contains 1,000 patient records, a common split might allocate 700 for training, 100 for validation, and 200 for testing.
 - Training set: Used to train the machine learning model, allowing it to learn patterns from the data.
 - Validation set: Used to tune model parameters and select the best model configuration without touching the test data.
 - Test set: Used to evaluate the final performance of the trained model on unseen data to estimate how well it will generalize to new cases.
- **Validation:** The process of evaluating a predictive model's performance on data not used during model development, to assess its generalizability and reliability in real-world clinical settings. Validation helps determine whether the model can accurately predict outcomes in new patients or populations. It includes techniques such as internal validation (e.g., cross-validation or bootstrapping within the development dataset) and external validation (testing the model on entirely independent datasets). Proper validation is essential to ensure that predictive models maintain their accuracy, clinical utility, and safety across diverse healthcare environments.
- **Validation Cycle:** A structured, repeatable process for assessing the external validity, safety, and clinical relevance of an AI model using local real-world data. A validation cycle involves an independent evaluation round — either pre-deployment or post-deployment — designed to verify that model performance remains robust, fair, and clinically meaningful within the target healthcare context. Each cycle typically uses temporally distinct or updated local data to detect potential performance degradation, data drift, concept drift, or emerging biases over time. Validation cycles may use different data aggregation strategies:
 - Cumulative cycles monitor stability trends over time, aggregating all available data to confirm robustness (common in clinical governance).
 - Non-cumulative (rolling) cycles focus on detecting short-term drifts or recent performance shifts by evaluating consecutive data windows.

A good practice is to alternate cumulative and rolling evaluations, combining long-term stability assessment with sensitivity to recent changes. In risk-based governance frameworks, the frequency and scope of validation cycles should be proportionate to the model's risk classification, observed performance trends, and clinical impact.